

“Summaries of Implemented Co-Creation Projects with Statistics on the Co-Creation Teams”

DELIVERABLE
D3.2

Version 01
07 2025

Project Number: 101070297

Project Acronym: INDUSAC

Project title: Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations

Starting date: 01/09/2022

Duration in months: 36

Call (part) identifier: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-20

Technical reference

<i>Deliverable:</i> 3.2	
<i>Work Package:</i>	3
<i>Due Date:</i>	M36
<i>Submission Date:</i>	23/07/2025
<i>Start Date of Project:</i>	01/09/2022
<i>Duration of Project:</i>	36 months
<i>Organisation Responsible for Deliverable:</i>	Jozef Stefan Institute
<i>Version:</i>	1.0
<i>Status:</i>	Final
<i>Author name(s):</i>	Duško Odić, Urška Mrgole, Marjeta Trobec
<i>Reviewer(s):</i>	INDUSAC partners and the INDUSAC Steering Committee
<i>Type:</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Report <input type="checkbox"/> Other
<i>Dissemination level:</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU <input type="checkbox"/> SEN

History of Changes:

Date	Comments	Version
10 July 2025	<i>initial draft by partners responsible</i>	V0.1
16 July 2025	<i>draft based on feedback from project partners</i>	V0.2
22 July 2025	<i>draft based on feedback from Steering Committee</i>	V0.3
23 July 2025	<i>final version submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V1.0

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components were successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. INDUSAC created a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including companies, students and researchers. INDUSAC achieved a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that leveraged the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

This deliverable contains the summaries of implemented co-creation projects carried out by co-creation teams and under supervision by the companies. Each summary is a combination of the required task, as summarised from the Challenge in question, and a summary of project results, as provided by the co-creation teams and companies. The deliverable also contains statistics on co-creation teams. 318 individuals in 164 teams of students and researchers participated in the INDUSAC project. Majority of teams (67.7 %) included three members and majority of individuals (44.0 %) participated in one team. Most teams (138 out of 164) were composed of students only. Gender distribution was 48.9 % female, 46.3 % male, and 4.8 % would-rather-not-say. EU widening countries had 61.5 % overall representation by country of residency and 69.3 % by country of students' university in the co-creation teams. By area of study, majority of students were from the Information Science and Engineering (around 30 %), and Economic Sciences fields (around 23 %). While most of the Challenges being solved (around 46 %) of were in the field of marketing campaign (PCA type 3 – Marketing campaign of the future), and around 18 % were focused on product development (PCA type 8 - Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain).

LIST OF ACRONYMS

2PP	two-photon polymerisation
ABS	anti-lock braking system
AEPAP	Advanced Engineering Prototypes to Actual Production
AI	artificial intelligence
AICM	AI-Driven Circularity Manager
AOP	advanced oxidation process
AR	augmented reality
ARM	Advanced RISC (reduced instruction set computer) Machines
B2B	business-to-business
B2C	business-to-consumer
BET	Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (surface area analysis)
BEV	battery electric vehicle
CMS	Content management system
CNAB	Club Natació Atlètic-Barceloneta
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets (language)
D	deliverable
DES	Deep Eutectic Solvent
DLS	dynamic light scattering
DS18B20	Dallas Semiconductor (temperature sensor model)
ECIU	European Consortium of Innovative Universities
EPR	extended producer responsibility
ESG	environmental, social, and governance
ESP32	wireless chip (developed by Espressif from China)
EU	European Union
EV	electric vehicle
F6S	platform for application management
FTIR	Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
GR	government relations
HCG	Healthy Cities Generator
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
IAC	industry-academia collaboration
IIoT	industrial internet of things
INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations
IoT	Internet of things

KIC	knowledge innovation community
KTH	Kungliga Tekniska högskolan (Royal Institute of Technology)
LLM	Large language model
M	month
MBR	membrane bioreactor
MCO	construction / furniture company from Cyprus
MES	manufacturing execution system
MOHU	waste management company in Hungary
MRC	Modular Reusable Crate
NCS	Natural Colour System (colour coding)
NGO	non-governmental organisation
NLC	nanostructured lipid carrier
OEE	Overall Equipment Effectiveness
PCA	Pre-defined collaborative approach
PCB REC	printed circuit board recycling
PCB	printed circuit board
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Sociological, Technological, Legal and Environmental
PET	positron emission tomography
PHB	Polyhydroxybutyrate
PLA	Polylactic Acid
PP	polypropylene
PSS	product service system
QR	quick response
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
RAL	Reichs-Ausschuss für Lieferbedingungen und Gütesicherung (colour coding)
ReactJS	React Java script
RFID	Radio-frequency identification
RMF	Robotics in Manufacturing Fundamentals
ROS	Robot operating system
SAP	software production company (Systemanalyse Programmentwicklung)
SEM	scanning electron microscopy / Search engine marketing
SEO	search engine optimisation
SME	small-to-medium enterprise
SNEDDS	Self-Nanoemulsifying Drug Delivery System
SSH	Secure shell
SWOT	strengths weaknesses opportunities threats
UF/NF	ultrafiltration/nanofiltration
UHPLC	ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography
UI/UX	user interface / user experience

USD	US dollar
UV	ultraviolet (light)
virCPB	gamified online cardiopulmonary bypass training programme
WebRTC	Web real-time communication
xMED	modular medical unit
XRD	X-ray diffraction

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT	3
ABSTRACT	4
LIST OF ACRONYMS.....	5
I. INTRODUCTION	9
II. SUMMARIES OF IMPLEMENTED CO-CREATION PROJECTS.....	10
III. STATISTICS ON CO-CREATION TEAMS.....	87
IV. FINAL REMARKS AND CONCLUSIONS.....	93
V. LIST OF FIGURES	94
VI. LIST OF TABLES.....	95

I. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable contains the summaries of implemented co-creation projects carried out by co-creation teams and under supervision by the companies. Each summary is a combination of the required task, as summarised from the Challenge in question, and a summary of project results, as provided by the co-creation teams and companies. The deliverable also contains statistics on co-creation teams.

II. SUMMARIES OF IMPLEMENTED CO-CREATION PROJECTS

Below is a list of implemented co-creation project summaries. Each summary contains the co-creation team ID, title of the Challenge, a summary of the required task, and a summary of project results. Summaries of results were compiled based on responses provided by the co-creation teams and companies through the INDUSAC questionnaires. The content was initially processed with the support of AI-based language tools to enhance consistency, eliminate repetitive phrasing, and convert first-person narratives into third-person summaries. These drafts were then manually reviewed and refined by the INDUSAC team to ensure clarity and neutrality, removing any direct references to company names or personal experiences. For challenges addressed by multiple teams, individual summaries are provided to reflect each team's contributions.

Team ID **247090**

Challenge: Removal Of Micropollutants From Municipal Wastewater

Summary of Challenge: prepare an experimental work programme and provide an analytical measurement background for removal of micropollutants; set up experimental tools and equipment, procure critical components and materials; conduct experimental work, risk analysis, economic calculations: payback period, maintenance costs. If a novel solution is developed, prepare intellectual property protection documentation

Short description of results: The team aimed to identify the most efficient technology for removing micropollutants, such as pesticides and pharmaceuticals, from wastewater, with a focus on enhancing environmental sustainability and public health. After reviewing current technologies, they determined that an advanced UF/NF membrane bioreactor (MBR) system offers the best balance of efficiency and cost-effectiveness, particularly for pharmaceutical removal. The project involved testing and optimising removal methods, followed by an economic analysis that considered equipment costs, maintenance, and operational expenses. This assessment ensured that the proposed solution was both technically viable and financially sustainable. The final recommendation is a hybrid MBR system that integrates membrane bioreactors with complementary technologies such as adsorption, reverse osmosis, advanced oxidation processes (AOP), or ultrafiltration, tailored to improve overall treatment performance.

Team ID 273053

Challenge: Aluminum oxide powder with active surface to be used as catalyst in other chemical processes

Summary of Challenge: add some active element during production, which would adhere (bind) to the large surface of the company's product Al_2O_3 to obtain a new product

Short description of results: As part of the challenge, the team explored the development of a value-added catalyst from aluminium oxide, leveraging its natural properties to reduce particle size and increase active surface area. They produced a general overview of aluminium oxide and its potential applications, followed by two documents proposing process solutions tailored to the company's interests. The team also conducted a brief SWOT analysis and compiled a list of relevant companies in Slovenia and Europe that utilise catalysts containing aluminium oxide.

Team ID 302081

Challenge: Marketing campaign for green mobile solution RollJet

Summary of Challenge: launch a marketing campaign that not only increases global sales but also raises awareness in the field of children's transportation

Short description of results: The "Rolljet Art Tour" project envisions a self-guided scooter tour linking major art museums and galleries across French cities, combining eco-friendly mobility with cultural exploration. The team developed a mobile app interface for curated tour routes and designed a targeted marketing strategy, supported by market research and a detailed PESTLE analysis of France and other EU countries. A promotional campaign for Rolljet scooters was also tailored to the French market. The initiative addresses the growing demand for active lifestyles and cultural engagement, offering a service that encourages both tourists and locals to explore their surroundings sustainably.

Team ID 312097

Challenge: Precious Nanoparticles and Their Applications

Summary of Challenge: assessment and identification of markets and applications where high purity nanoparticles made from precious metals can be applied (e.g., sensors or markers, or pastes and inks used in 3D printing)

Short description of results: The project resulted in an extensive review analysing the potential applications of precious nanoparticles across various fields. The final report includes a detailed comparison of laser-based nanoparticle production with other existing methods, outlining key advantages, limitations, process yield, and cost considerations. It

highlights scenarios where laser-produced nanoparticles are preferred, supported by recent scientific findings. Potential applications in environmental remediation, coatings, and agriculture are also explored, providing a comprehensive overview of the method's strengths and suitability for future innovation.

Team ID **330066**

Challenge: Battery electric vehicles - product opportunities

Summary of Challenge: alignment of required knowledge about BEV components with the supplier's existing expertise; identify new opportunities in the BEV market and strategically address them

Short description of results: The project focused on identifying an innovative, manufacturable product for the Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV) market and developing a strategy for the company's market entry. The team conducted research on battery technologies, compared electric and internal combustion powertrains, and explored thermal management solutions to improve efficiency. A global market analysis informed product positioning, while the team proposed an In-Wheel Motor with Regenerative Braking and ABS, along with suggestions for cost-effective EV components and materials. The result was a clear, research-based roadmap to support the company's competitive entry into the BEV sector.

Team ID **356074**

Challenge: Recycling Gazek Safety Products – Responsibility for All, for Everything

Summary of Challenge: explore how fall safety equipment (e.g., safety harnesses) can be recycled - propose specific recycling recommendations

Short description of results: Three alternatives were developed at the idea level, and the Persona for Alternative 2 and Alternative 3 was completed.

Team ID **366074**

Challenge: Recycling Gazek Safety Products – Responsibility for All, for Everything

Summary of Challenge: explore how fall safety equipment (e.g., safety harnesses) can be recycled - propose specific recycling recommendations

Short description of results: The team developed recycling solutions for a company dealing with diverse safety equipment waste. After characterising the waste materials, they assessed both in-house and outsourced recycling options. A comprehensive report was

produced, detailing material composition, relevant legislation, and case studies of similar recycling efforts. Findings showed that establishing an in-house recycling facility would be economically unfeasible given the low volume of waste and high setup costs. Instead, the recommended approach involves collaborating with a third-party provider via Hungary's MOHU platform, in line with recent extended producer responsibility (EPR) regulations. The team supported their recommendation with cost projections, a list of potential partners, and insights from consultations with university experts, government representatives, and recycling professionals. An on-site visit to a recycling facility further informed the final proposal. The project delivered a realistic and sustainable waste management strategy tailored to the company's needs.

Team ID **402093**

Challenge: pla:Fi the innovative pillow, marketing campaign

Summary of Challenge: educate and introduce the product (pillow) to the market

Short description of results: The team prepared a marketing campaign for the company to promote its product - pla:Fi, focusing on increasing brand awareness. They started by getting to know the product, finding the first ideas, and finding the target group. They created marketing personas, different analysis (e.g., SWOT analysis) and at the end a marketing campaign with ideas for promotion (e.g., where the product can be promoted). They focused on a marketing campaign aiming at students.

Team ID **443055**

Challenge: ReSoil® Web Revamp: Greening The Future By Restoring Degraded Land Worldwide

Summary of Challenge: redesigning and redeveloping the company's website

Short description of results: The project focused on redesigning the company's website to align with its advanced technology for washing soil contaminated with heavy metals. the project addresses the remediation of polluted urban, industrial, and residential terrains, with a strong emphasis on protecting vulnerable populations, particularly children, from the harmful effects of heavy metal exposure. As part of the revamp, the team developed new front-end systems and integrated tools to support enhanced website functionalities. A responsive and user-centric design was implemented to improve navigation, visuals, and accessibility. In addition, potential case study sites with lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), and arsenic (As) contamination, across the EU, Middle East, and Asia, were identified to guide research and remediation efforts. Educational materials on heavy metal pollution were also revised, offering clearer, more comprehensive information to the public.

Team ID **447068**

Challenge: Robot fleet manager from open-source software

Summary of Challenge: package open-sourced solutions with other components of warehouse robots and set up for a particular scenario to be useful

Short description of results: The project aimed to develop a fleet management system enabling coordinated communication and task management across multiple robots. The team was tasked with integrating Open RMF, an open-source fleet manager, for a company exploring multi-robot coordination. Core functionalities included route deconfliction, task dispatching, and centralised robot control. Initial challenges arose from compatibility issues across Ubuntu and ROS 2 versions, which were resolved by using Ubuntu 24 and ROS 2 Rolling. Binary installation of Open RMF failed, prompting a switch to source code installation, which encountered additional obstacles on ARM architecture used by Raspberry Pi devices. The final solution involved using Docker on the server and removing unsupported packages on the client side. The team successfully installed Ubuntu on the Raspberry Pis, set up SSH connections, installed ROS 2, and built Open RMF from source on both server (PC) and client devices. A dashboard was also developed to control navigation and task execution. By integrating the company's platforms with Open RMF, the system significantly enhanced robot coordination and operational efficiency.

Team ID **482069**

Challenge: Marketing campaign for metalized/conductive yarns

Summary of Challenge: analyse the market: the potential market size, key players on the market (competitors), identify the users of conductive yarns, identify the supply chain

Short description of results: The research explored the technical properties and commercial potential of thermoregulating conductive yarns for use in technical textiles. These yarns offer effective heating and cooling capabilities, improving comfort across applications such as wearable technology, sportswear, and automotive interiors. Key benefits include moisture control, energy-efficient heating, and customisable thermal comfort. Market analysis indicated significant growth potential, particularly in the wearable tech and automotive sectors, where continued advancements in materials and technologies are expected.

Team ID **484098**

Challenge: Age-friendly banking and fraud prevention

Summary of Challenge: find technical (data or behavioural driven) solutions to empower consumers, especially older adults, to manage their finances more efficiently and protect them from financial exploitation through scams

Short description of results: The Project resulted in a solution for elderly people to manage their finances, enable secure banking, and prevent fraud and cybercrimes. The team collected data and prepared a platform.

Team ID **649049**

Challenge: Advancements In Orthopaedic And Dental Implant Surface Treatments

Summary of Challenge: explore orthopaedic and dental implant manufacturing technologies, analysing market trends across Europe, Asia, and America. Identify and analyse potential customers among global implant manufacturers

Short description of results: The project delivered key insights into the dental implants market, emphasising advancements in surface treatments that enhance osseointegration, contributing to a projected market growth to USD 7.2 billion by 2032. The team also identified emerging trends, including the rise of dental tourism and growing demand for durable solutions and improved surface treatments. A scenario trend analysis was conducted to assess market growth and technological developments.

Team ID **656042**

Challenge: Marketing Campaign For An Energy Efficient Office Building In A Hungarian County Capital

Summary of Challenge: develop a marketing campaign to attract businesses to the office building - developing a tangible package of complex services

Short description of results: The project focused on developing a marketing campaign for an energy-efficient office building in Pécs, Hungary, starting with a comprehensive SWOT analysis. The team identified strengths such as environmental benefits and cost savings, along with weaknesses like vacancy rates. They explored opportunities linked to rising ESG compliance and assessed threats such as shifting work trends. By analysing market conditions, customer segments, and emerging trends, the team proposed strategic recommendations to improve occupancy, enhance tenant satisfaction, and reduce operational costs. The resulting campaign included clear goals, value propositions,

suggested marketing channels, and performance metrics. These insights support sustainable, inclusive building management and strengthen the company's market position.

Team ID **778078**

Challenge: Developing virtual bar cafe of the future

Summary of Challenge: develop thorough description of the virtual bar cafe, which activities should be offered, how the bar cafe would function, etc. Special attention should be on socialising and experience

Short description of results: The project resulted in the development of the “Virtual Bar Café of the Future”, an innovative digital social hub designed to connect users worldwide through immersive and accessible virtual experiences. Built using modern web technologies, the platform features customisable spaces for events like concerts and workshops, alongside an in-game purchasing system to simulate a real café atmosphere. The team designed an interactive, device-responsive front end, ensuring seamless performance and enabling dynamic updates for future enhancements. Additional efforts included detailed research on user behaviour and social dynamics to support an inclusive and flexible user experience, as well as the creation of SEO-friendly blog articles to support the platform's visibility and growth.

Team ID **878055**

Challenge: ReSoil® Web Revamp: Greening The Future By Restoring Degraded Land Worldwide

Summary of Challenge: redesigning and redeveloping the company's website

Short description of results: The project successfully organised and structured global data on soil contamination and companies specialising in remediation, resulting in two key resources: a comprehensive interactive contamination map based on international studies and a structured dossier of soil remediation companies. These tools offer centralised, accessible information to support future research, policymaking, and informed decision-making in environmental management. While the project did not provide direct solutions to contamination, it created a valuable foundation for collaboration among researchers, policymakers, and industry professionals. The team focused on accurate data collection, validation, and presentation, ensuring consistency and user-friendly access. Contributions from all members were essential in building a clear, reliable, and practical resource for environmental stakeholders.

Team ID **955044**

Challenge: Increasing Social Media Popularity In The Non-Profit Sector

Summary of Challenge: increase number of followers on the cluster's Facebook page and on LinkedIn.

Short description of results: The solution encompassed trend and scenario analysis, target group analysis, persona methods with templates, marketing campaign design, post planning in Canva, and a detailed analysis of the Facebook page. These elements, along with clear recommendations, enabled the development of an actionable marketing strategy, supported by ready-to-use content. The team created a new digital menu and proposed additional services, contributing to a refreshed brand offering. The team enhanced digital presence by boosting social media engagement, showcasing industrial achievements, and promoting regional collaboration. The campaign resulted in increased engagement rates and follower growth, reinforcing the cluster's visibility and community impact. A key project focus was understanding social media trends and engagement strategies to attract younger professionals interested in career opportunities. Target group analyses and tailored marketing plans revealed that personalised content, platform-specific strategies (especially for LinkedIn, Instagram, and TikTok), and interactive media such as videos and quizzes significantly improve engagement. The findings emphasised organic growth, consistent content delivery, event-driven engagement, and precise targeting. Automation tools, including auto-invites and sponsored campaigns, were recommended to support follower acquisition. Strategic content enhancements and AI optimisation opportunities were also proposed. This comprehensive analysis informed practical recommendations for campaign improvement and alignment with evolving trends in career development and digital marketing. The team also implemented a campaign for a non-profit organisation, including research and content creation tailored to its mission.

Team ID **958043**

Challenge: SWOT Analysis Of An Energy Efficient Office Building In Operation In A County Capital Of Hungary

Summary of Challenge: a SWOT analysis of an office building

Short description of results: The project delivered a comprehensive SWOT analysis for an energy-efficient office building in Hungary, highlighting strengths such as sustainability and modern infrastructure, and identifying weaknesses like high vacancy rates. Opportunities were found in the rise of ESG compliance, while threats included remote work trends. The team synthesised internal and external market data to facilitate the analysis and developed strategic recommendations aimed at improving occupancy, enhancing tenant satisfaction, and optimising revenue. These insights will support sustainable operations, attract ESG-

conscious tenants, and strengthen the company's market position as a leader in green innovation.

Team ID **1522094**

Challenge: The Global Perfusion Gaming Tournament

Summary of Challenge: develop a marketing campaign, conceptualise and orchestrate a global gaming tournament tailored for cardiovascular perfusion students

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive global gaming tournament model for virCPB, a virtual perfusion training platform. The proposed solution combined educational simulation with competitive gameplay, aiming to boost medical knowledge through interactive challenges. Key elements included tournament structure, scoring mechanics, stakeholder engagement, and media outreach to maximise visibility and participation. The initiative promotes cross-institutional collaboration, student engagement, and broader awareness of digital health tools in medical education. It offers a scalable and replicable model suitable for national and international rollout, with potential to generate valuable data for research and innovation.

Team ID **1800101**

Challenge: Future approaches in organic skincare marketing initiatives

Summary of Challenge: marketing strategies in skincare industry; promoting advanced organic skincare

Short description of results: During the »Future Approaches in Organic Skincare Marketing Initiatives« project, the team applied targeted marketing strategies to enhance brand visibility and online presence. Key activities included producing scientific and informative blog content, sharing market insights, and redesigning the website to better engage target audiences while elevating brand awareness and image. Product photography was updated to offer a more realistic and visually appealing representation. The team also gathered feedback from target groups, enabling ongoing improvements in product formulation and alignment with market expectations.

Team ID **1800132**

Challenge: New Ideas To Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches

Summary of Challenge: revolutionising the company's approach to promoting advanced organic skincare

Short description of results: The project centered on developing concise, informative blogs covering topics such as supplements, nutrients, skin biology, and skincare innovations. These articles supported trend monitoring and promoted scientifically grounded consumer awareness. The team also launched social media campaigns, conducted a competitor analysis of supplement brands, and surveyed users to better understand their behaviours and expectations. Influencers were researched for potential collaborations, and client feedback was integrated throughout. These efforts established a strong, consistent online presence and laid the foundation for the skincare brand's future growth.

Team ID **1800202**

Challenge: New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare

Summary of Challenge: develop marketing strategies in skincare industry;
revolutionising promotion of advanced organic skincare

Short description of results: The team implemented targeted marketing strategies outlined in the project. They developed science-based, informative blogs and shared market insights that significantly enhanced social media visibility. High-quality photos, reels, and videos were produced to present the products and the spa in a realistic and aesthetically appealing way. Weekly newsletters were created to maintain consistent communication and strengthen customer relationships. The team defined a clear visual approach for product photography and reel creation, researched competitor newsletter structures, and identified the most effective methods for implementing newsletters. The project successfully delivered solutions for improved marketing pathways and deeper customer engagement.

Team ID **2230201**

Challenge: Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations

Summary of Challenge: improve the body's ability to absorb fisetin, a flavonoid known for its anti-aging and anti-inflammatory properties

Short description of results: The project focused on optimising methods for studying fisetin, a flavonoid with notable health benefits, by identifying nanocarriers that improve its bioavailability and absorption. The team explored both in vitro and in vivo analysis techniques, noting that while in vivo methods offer higher precision and relevance, they are more complex and cost-intensive. Extensive research was conducted on various liposome-like and nanovesicle carriers, including ethosomes, transethosomes, and transfersomes. These were evaluated for their potential in enhancing fisetin delivery, particularly through topical and transdermal routes. Techniques such as DLS, SEM, and Franz diffusion cell experiments confirmed improvements in fisetin's stability, skin penetration, and therapeutic

potential, especially for pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications. The project also developed an innovative gel-based formulation using binary ethosomes and natural ingredients like chitosan to optimise delivery and product stability. Literature reviews supported further exploration into transdermal delivery systems, including the encapsulation of fisetin in ethosomes. To communicate findings to a wider audience, the team produced accessible scientific blogs focused on fisetin's antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity, suitable delivery systems, and the role of peptides in skincare. These efforts not only enhanced public understanding but also increased the visibility of the project and its innovative outcomes.

Team ID **2230311**

Challenge: Researching Innovative Approaches for Enhancing Skincare Formulation

Summary of Challenge: develop optimised skincare formulations that enhance topical efficacy; researching existing patents and products, investigating synergistic effects of various active ingredients; analysing formulation composition, evaluating delivery strategies, and utilising advanced analytical methods to determine multi-component absorption and penetration without conducting direct absorption testing

Short description of results: The team successfully advanced the development of an innovative bioactive skincare formulation using natural antioxidants encapsulated in nanostructured carriers. The project focused on creating a gel-based cosmetic product featuring fisetin, a natural antioxidant with anti-aging properties, delivered through ethosomal nanocarriers. Binary ethosomes were identified as the most efficient and stable system, offering strong potential for industrial application. A chitosan-based gel was selected for its biocompatibility and synergistic benefits in skin care. A multidisciplinary approach, integrating chemistry, biochemistry, and pharmacology, was employed to identify effective ingredients, optimise delivery systems for enhanced skin absorption, and evaluate the synergistic potential of flavonoids such as quercetin, kaempferol, and myricetin. Due to limited fisetin-specific research, structurally similar flavonoids were also analysed to assess bioavailability in topical formulations. The team conducted an in-depth literature review, assessed relevant patents, analysed regulatory pathways, and proposed a clear commercialisation and product classification strategy. Key phases for prototype development were defined, setting the foundation for future product refinement. Individual contributions included research on encapsulation techniques, identification of suitable gelling agents, analysis of flavonoid absorption data, and evaluation of intellectual property related to transdermal gel formulations. This collaborative effort resulted in a well-structured roadmap for creating stable, effective, and eco-friendly skincare solutions with strong commercial potential.

Team ID **2710109**

Challenge: Development Of A Chlorine-Free Water Disinfection System

Summary of Challenge: develop cheap and easy-to-use method of disinfecting water beyond chlorine

Short description of results: To support the development of a chlorine-free water disinfection system, the team conducted a survey of existing solutions to identify key features, limitations, and user preferences. Additional market research was carried out to benchmark competing products and understand customer pain points. These insights informed the design of a more effective, user-oriented solution. The team collaborated closely, combining product research and customer feedback to guide development in line with market expectations.

Team ID **2730197**

Challenge: AI Assistants: Automating and Streamlining Engineering Processes

Summary of Challenge: develop custom AI assistants using RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation) technology to streamline engineering workflows in the automotive sector

Short description of results: The project successfully delivered a robust and privacy-focused AI solution designed to enhance automation, efficiency, and sustainability in engineering and industrial workflows. Central to the solution is the integration of Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), supporting improved document processing and contextual accuracy while maintaining strict compliance with GDPR through on-site data handling. The system features multi-LLM integration, a scalable architecture adaptable to both standard and high-performance hardware setups, and user-friendly functionalities such as drag-and-drop document uploads. These capabilities lay a strong foundation for ongoing enhancements, including the future integration of a local LLM to ensure confidential data remains secure on-site. The team played a key role in testing and configuring the RAG setup using the AnythingLLM tool, optimising system performance across platforms, and refining AI-assisted search tools to support faster, more accurate access to safety data. Their collaborative effort advanced technical implementation, system design, and documentation, providing actionable solutions and a valuable platform for future developments.

Team ID **2830167**

Challenge: Tennis academy assistant

Summary of Challenge: develop a business model for providing a system where video analysis of tennis players provides data on body movement and ball movement, to provide statistics of the ball movement in relation to the body movement of the player

Short description of results: The project evaluated the potential of an AI-driven data solution for tennis training, highlighting its strong value in enhancing coaching and player performance. The team assessed market readiness, adoption barriers, and economic viability, and provided strategic recommendations to support inclusive and accessible implementation for users worldwide.

Team ID **3990347**

Challenge: Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z"

Summary of Challenge: analyse students' and young adults' investment preferences; adapt existing products (at more applicable fees and other product flexibilities) and design an investment solution within company's regulatory restrictions

Short description of results: The project successfully developed a concept for Gip-Z, a digital financial product tailored to Gen Z investors in North Macedonia. The solution emphasises intuitive design, gamification, educational content, and sustainability-focused investment options to promote financial literacy and responsible investing. Extensive market and user research, covering global practices, competitor analysis, and persona development, formed the foundation of the product concept. The team's research-based approach set the groundwork for future product development, despite current legislative limitations in the region. The design phase was aligned closely with development and strategic planning, ensuring the solution reflects the real needs and digital habits of Gen Z. The outcome is a ready-to-prototype concept with strong potential for future implementation.

Team ID **4000119**

Challenge: Innovative diversification: broadening horizons in die casting toolmaking

Summary of Challenge: diversify the production and service offerings of the company's small boutique die casting tool manufacturing company; identifying potential new directions for growth

Short description of results: The project successfully developed advanced smart moulds with integrated AI and IoT capabilities to enhance real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and overall efficiency in die casting technology. The team conducted in-depth

research on mould types and die casting variables, informing the selection of optimal mould designs for various manufacturing processes. Smart moulds were equipped with sensors and heat exchange circuits to measure critical parameters such as temperature, pressure, and wear in real time. This enabled precise process control, optimised solidification through controlled cooling, and significantly reduced defects. AI and machine learning models were implemented to support predictive maintenance and mould selection, improving operational precision and efficiency. Modular and adjustable mould designs reduced production time and costs, while custom software solutions facilitated sensor data analysis for quality improvement. The team also identified and sourced appropriate sensors tailored to the project's needs. These innovations positioned the company at the forefront of smart mould technology, expanding its consulting capabilities, increasing the value of its mould offerings, and enhancing competitiveness in the market.

Team ID **4090101**

Challenge: Future approaches in organic skincare marketing initiatives

Summary of Challenge: marketing strategies in skincare industry; promoting advanced organic skincare

Short description of results: The team aimed to revolutionise the promotion of advanced organic skincare by introducing innovative and distinctive marketing tactics. The project included developing website content such as video materials, booking services, a price list, and customisable gift vouchers. Photoshoots were organised to showcase both skincare products and the spa environment, while a comprehensive marketing analysis identified trends that informed the strategy. The team also created and managed engaging social media content, running a campaign to strengthen the skincare brand's digital presence. These coordinated efforts established a strong foundation for the brand's future growth and visibility.

Team ID **4090132**

Challenge: New Ideas To Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches

Summary of Challenge: revolutionising the company's approach to promoting advanced organic skincare

Short description of results: The team successfully implemented a comprehensive social media marketing campaign to promote the company's advanced organic skincare line. Activities included engaging content creation, professional photoshoots, targeted social media posts, and in-depth marketing analysis. The campaign enhanced the brand's online presence and gathered valuable customer feedback, laying a strong foundation for future growth.

Team ID **4090202**

Challenge: New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare

Summary of Challenge: develop marketing strategies in skincare industry;
revolutionising promotion of advanced organic skincare

Short description of results: The project significantly enhanced the company's skincare brand marketing strategy by strengthening its digital presence. A new website with online booking and voucher functionalities offered a seamless customer experience, supported by bilingual content and detailed blog posts explaining each product's ingredients, benefits, and skincare relevance. Comprehensive market research, competitor analysis, and engaging social media campaigns boosted brand visibility, customer engagement, and business growth. The team researched marketing strategies, overseeing photoshoots, and creating website content.

Team ID **4160181**

Challenge: Protective working equipment

Summary of Challenge: addressing the company's stock-related challenges, e.g., insufficient stock availability or negative stock levels, to accurately represent stock levels on the website and enable customers to seamlessly add items to their shopping baskets

Short description of results: The team collaborated with a company specialising in protective workwear to address stock management challenges and improve overall operational efficiency. By analysing inventory data, they identified discrepancies, including duplicated and outdated entries, and proposed streamlined procedures to enable accurate, real-time stock tracking. The recommended solution emphasised the adoption of digital tools such as SAP Business One with Extended Warehouse Management to enhance traceability and support the company's sustainability goals. Additional recommendations included improvements to the company's website, targeting segmented audiences more effectively and suggesting a full redesign to align with brand positioning and user experience best practices. Team members contributed to system analysis, communication coordination, and the development of practical, actionable recommendations. The project not only delivered strategic insights for the company but also strengthened the team's skills in digital collaboration, business analysis, and integrated resource planning.

Team ID 4410255

Challenge: Project Brief for IKEA: Designing the Marketing Campaign for Sustainability-Conscious Consumers

Summary of Challenge: designing an innovative and forward-thinking marketing campaign for the company

Short description of results: The team developed an integrated marketing campaign for the company focused on promoting circular living and sustainability through clear, engaging, and legally compliant messaging. The campaign combined two initiatives, Circular Living and Back to Life, and highlighted services such as Buyback, Spare Parts, Trixig repair kits, and Pre-owned furniture to encourage responsible consumption and make sustainable choices more accessible to everyday customers. The strategy blended digital and in-store activations to reflect the company's core values of affordability, inclusivity, and environmental responsibility. Messaging was crafted to resonate with customer insights and current sustainability trends, while carefully avoiding greenwashing. Team contributions included shaping the creative direction, writing sustainability-focused content, analysing customer behaviour, and ensuring alignment with regulatory standards. The campaign offered a meaningful opportunity to merge strategic thinking with purpose-driven communication, supporting the company's commitment to circularity and environmental impact.

Team ID 4410300

Challenge: Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare

Summary of Challenge: innovative marketing strategies for social media in the oversaturated skincare industry

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive B2B marketing strategy for the company, targeting retailers, dermatologists, and spas. The strategy supported international expansion and reflected the brand's luxury positioning, scientific credibility, and commitment to sustainability. Key deliverables included a targeted email campaign, nano-influencer outreach plan, social media strategy, and website enhancement suggestions. Additionally, the team produced professional content such as a whitepaper, blog post, and tailored product messaging for international partners. Contributions spanned content creation, influencer research, and the structuring of communication materials. Visuals and messaging were carefully aligned with the brand's identity to ensure consistency and impact across all touchpoints. The result was a cohesive, strategic package designed to strengthen B2B outreach and elevate global brand recognition.

Team ID **4430174**

Challenge: Redesign And Updating Envit's ReSoil® Website To Enhance Global Engagement And Accessibility

Summary of Challenge: redesign the company website to enhance global engagement; enable easy content management, detailed tech info, case studies, video demos, and simple animations

Short description of results: The team redesigned the company's website into a user-friendly platform with an intuitive interface and improved functionality. New content was developed and integrated, including detailed sections on the company's technology, updated case studies, multimedia content, and subpages to clearly communicate benefits. A new leaflet for the Mobile Commercial Plant for inner-city on-site treatment was also added to improve accessibility and engagement. The content was designed to be clear, unbiased, and inclusive, ensuring equitable access to information. The project successfully fostered stakeholder collaboration and advanced sustainable industry solutions through innovative research and practical implementation.

Team ID **4470140**

Challenge: Sustainability Challenge: Reducing Waste In Abrasive Materials Production

Summary of Challenge: develop solutions that repurpose or recycle waste from abrasive belt production, either by transforming it into new products or by reclaiming raw materials

Short description of results: The project aimed to repurpose abrasive material waste from abrasive belt production into a valuable raw material. After evaluating various solutions, the company selected the production of 3D printing filament using aluminium oxide extracted from the waste. The team first developed a process for extracting aluminium oxide, followed by its application in filament manufacturing, offering an innovative and sustainable use of industrial by-products.

Team ID **4470239**

Challenge: Project 1: Product Utilizing Post-Production Regrind

Summary of Challenge: design a functional and aesthetically appealing product made from recycled plastic

Short description of results: The project introduced SnapLid, a reusable food container series made from recycled polypropylene (PP) regrind, aimed at reducing plastic waste through practical circular design. The containers are airtight, modular, and designed for eco-

conscious households and zero-waste retailers, balancing durability, food safety, and affordability. The solution integrates traceable QR-coded packaging to promote sustainability and transparency. The team conducted user research, developed product personas, and co-created a marketing concept centred on consumer storytelling. They also defined key product features to ensure alignment with environmental goals and regulatory standards.

Team ID **4610193**

Challenge: Developing a Smart Colour Identification Online/Mobile App

Summary of Challenge: develop a user-friendly mobile or website application that allows customers to quickly identify Pantone, RAL, or NCS colour codes from photos or live camera feed

Short description of results: The project resulted in the development of a concept for a Smart Colour Identification online/mobile app, designed to accurately detect and match colours from various materials in real time. Aimed primarily at supporting industries such as plastics and design, the app enables users to obtain precise colour codes, analyse colours from uploaded images, and access a universal colour database. The team conducted thorough market research to assess the app's relevance and potential applications, identifying strong interest across several sectors. Despite facing challenges related to licensing and technical feasibility, the project offered valuable insights into digital colour recognition and its market potential. The outcome lays the groundwork for future development of advanced, user-friendly colour identification tools.

Team ID **4610203**

Challenge: Implementation of AI systems in the metal processing industry (small and medium sized production)

Summary of Challenge: implement AI systems in metal production processes, which would increase efficiency, reliability and quality processes

Short description of results: The project focused on integrating AI solutions into the manufacturing processes of the company to improve productivity, minimise downtime, and support sustainability objectives. Core outcomes included optimised production scheduling, predictive maintenance, enhanced product quality, and advanced data-driven decision-making, all aligned with Industry 4.0 standards. These innovations are expected to significantly increase efficiency and operational flexibility in small to medium batch production. The team prepared and delivered a comprehensive Business Plan, SWOT Analysis, and Benefits Report, outlining the strategic impact of AI integration. They researched applicable AI technologies, analysed production data, and proposed solutions

for predictive maintenance and energy optimisation. Additionally, they provided insights into the AI market and guided the company on how to align digital transformation with its long-term performance and environmental goals. This collaborative effort ensured that both the technical and strategic aspects of AI implementation were addressed, laying a strong foundation for innovation-driven growth at the company.

Team ID **4990191**

Challenge: Alveus kitchen sink: The centerpiece of your kitchen

Summary of Challenge: to understand the needs of kitchen retailers, developers as well as homeowners, renovators, and explore how evolving trends can reshape the role of the kitchen sink

Short description of results: The project successfully delivered a fresh and engaging B2B marketing campaign for the company, highlighting the brand's innovative kitchen sink solutions. Comprehensive campaign materials, including visually compelling assets and targeted messaging, were developed to strengthen brand identity and boost customer engagement. The team conducted a thorough analysis of the website, market trends, target personas, and other key factors to identify improvement opportunities. This research led to strategic recommendations for optimising site navigation, enhancing B2B engagement, and increasing lead generation. A standout feature of the campaign was its creative concept, linking kitchen sinks with theatre to craft a memorable and distinctive brand narrative. By blending practicality with creativity, the team developed a strategy that ensures market relevance, visual impact, and effective audience engagement. The results provide the company with actionable tools to strengthen its market position and better serve its professional clientele.

Team ID **5000105**

Challenge: Fun and easy to use "financial competence training & knowledge service" for people 50+

Summary of Challenge: develop technical concepts to easily (advertising free) educate older adults 50+ about financial knowledge

Short description of results: The team developed a mock-up prototype designed to enhance financial literacy among individuals aged 50 and above. The three-member group combined expertise in design and economics to create a user-friendly interface tailored to this demographic. The graphic designer produced intuitive and visually appealing mock-up designs, while the economics students conceptualised the service and conducted one-on-one interviews to align features with users' needs. The result is a targeted, accessible prototype that addresses financial education for an often-overlooked age group.

Team ID **6490231**

Challenge: Bioprinting - future technology for tissues and drugs

Summary of Challenge: improving the viability of cells during the 3D printing process

Short description of results: The project advanced personalised medicine by combining bioprinting of diseased tissues and 3D-printed microneedles for targeted, minimally invasive drug delivery. Through AI-driven optimisation of bioprinting parameters, such as cell viability, the team improved the accuracy of tissue models for drug testing and treatment planning. The work resulted in small-scale tissue constructs that mimic human organ function, offering a safer, faster, and more ethical alternative to animal testing. In parallel, the project explored the use of microneedles to enhance drug delivery efficiency and patient comfort. The team investigated biomaterials, bioinks, and the clinical relevance of these technologies to bridge medical application with technical innovation. Tasks were distributed to ensure smooth collaboration, with contributions ranging from researching bioprinting techniques and microneedle design, to preparing materials, analysing drug response, and facilitating academic-industry cooperation. The resulting strategy supports more precise disease modelling and therapeutic development, aligning with the future of ethical and effective biomedical research.

Team ID **6990103**

Challenge: Innovative Custom-Made Hardwood Floors

Summary of Challenge: marketing approach for the launch of custom-made floors

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive marketing strategy to support the launch of the company's premium flooring line, designed to reflect both a strong connection to nature and practical value for customers. Their work included market and buyer analysis, persona development, campaign planning, and identification of campaign requirements. Innovative ideas were proposed to strengthen brand awareness and positioning. The team also contributed to enhancing the "Essence" parquet collection by introducing practical, economically viable, and creative solutions that elevated its market appeal.

Team ID **7430170**

Challenge: MCO Marketing Campaign

Summary of Challenge: market analysis / design of marketing campaign; trend analysis combining future customers and marketing trends for a construction / furniture manufacturing company

Short description of results: The team developed a strategic marketing campaign to enhance the digital visibility of an architectural consulting firm based in Cyprus. The project included a detailed market analysis, identification of digital and sustainability trends, and formulation of a marketing approach tailored to the company's strengths. Key deliverables included target group analysis with customer personas, recommendations for website structure and content, and ideas for integrating the brand into social media platforms. The campaign emphasised MCO's personal, eco-conscious approach and offered actionable steps to improve online presence and audience engagement. The team also created structured documentation and visual materials to support implementation.

Team ID **7500174**

Challenge: Redesign And Updating Envit's ReSoil® Website To Enhance Global Engagement And Accessibility

Summary of Challenge: redesign the company website to enhance global engagement; enable easy content management, detailed tech info, case studies, video demos, and simple animations

Short description of results: The team successfully developed a new logo, email signature, and introduction letter, establishing a cohesive and modern visual identity for the company. They completed the design and implementation of a user-friendly, visually appealing website, along with a CMS platform that enables administrators to post news and case studies. In addition, they prepared case studies on contaminated soils, with a focus on European examples, to support the company's content strategy and enhance its online presence.

Team ID **7500196**

Challenge: Optimizing Envit's ReSoil® Website for Enhanced Performance, Branding, and User Experience

Summary of Challenge: transform the company's website into a high-performing, user-friendly platform

Short description of results: The project focused on enhancing the company's branding and communication by delivering a fully functional and visually appealing website. The team redesigned the company logo based on feedback and significantly improved the site's aesthetics and usability. A professional folder design was created, featuring adaptable and reusable illustrations aligned with the company's identity, contributing to a cohesive and modern brand presence.

Team ID **7500310**

Challenge: ReSoil® Website Digital Optimization, SEO Strategy, and User Engagement

Summary of Challenge: enhancing the performance and visibility of the ReSoil® website to support its mission and reach a wider audience

Short description of results: The team successfully completed a full website redesign, delivering a modern, user-friendly, and fully responsive interface optimised for all devices. The new site features improved usability, consistent branding, enhanced performance, and greater accessibility. SEO best practices were implemented, and the site was migrated to a new CMS to ensure easy content management for the client. Key deliverables included a finalised content structure and navigation blueprint, custom marketing banners, and a streamlined visual redesign.

Team ID **7580304**

Challenge: Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

Summary of Challenge: develop innovative strategies that combine photography, graphic design, video production, and content creation to craft cohesive marketing campaigns for natural skincare and luxury spa

Short description of results: The team enhanced the digital presence of the company by developing a cohesive visual and content strategy tailored to the brand's eco-luxury identity. The project focused on skincare and spa promotion through SEO-optimised blog articles, high-quality photographs and videos, and engaging social media reels. These efforts supported marketing goals, strengthened brand visibility, and increased online engagement. Content was designed to communicate product benefits and align with audience expectations. The team contributed to blog writing, video concept development, visual production, and the overall tone and style of the communication strategy. Coordination with the company ensured that the final materials met branding objectives while also improving operational efficiency and user engagement.

Team ID **7770139**

Challenge: Smart Tools

Summary of Challenge: designing an app for receiving and translating data from sensors of metal forming tools to an easily presentable language

Short description of results: The project aimed to develop a smart tool application connected to a cloud-based system for real-time communication with temperature and force sensors, designed for harsh industrial environments. The focus was on reducing

energy and material consumption in serial production by minimising emissions through advanced tooling solutions. Key innovations included the integration of sensors into the tooling and the development of a Wi-Fi-enabled application compatible with manufacturing execution systems (MES), enabling seamless data communication and predictive maintenance. The team designed the sensor integration, ensured MES compatibility, and created a user-friendly interface for monitoring critical parameters. These efforts resulted in a stable, efficient, and sustainable production process, positioning the company as a leader in smart tool technology and digitalised manufacturing.

Team ID **8550143**

Challenge: Product labelling of the future

Summary of Challenge: analyse impact of regulation and alternative labelling methods on label-converting industry; identify opportunities for label converters to become more sustainable, through material innovation, process optimisation, or exploring partnerships; develop solutions to meet regulations and explore the potential of alternative labelling methods; recommend strategies for label converters to adapt

Short description of results: The team conducted an in-depth analysis of competitors, sustainable materials, printing methods, and real-world examples of companies adopting eco-friendly packaging practices. Guided by European sustainability goals and regulations, they proposed actionable strategies such as repositioning the company as a sustainable labelling provider and investing in direct-to-packaging printing. By adopting the suggested trends and materials, the company can reduce waste, align with environmental standards, and strengthen its brand image as a responsible, eco-conscious business.

Team ID **8570291**

Challenge: Development and Execution of a Social Media Strategy for Tower Spa

Summary of Challenge: enhance Tower Spa's presence and interaction on popular social media platforms, including TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn

Short description of results: The team successfully developed and executed a comprehensive social media strategy for a heritage wellness destination, with the goal of enhancing brand visibility, engagement, and long-term digital growth. Drawing on in-depth market research and analysis of leading spa brands worldwide, the team identified key trends in wellness marketing and adapted them to highlight the spa's unique blend of medieval charm and modern luxury. The strategy was built around clearly defined content pillars – historical uniqueness, wellness innovation, luxury experiences, and inclusivity. A full-scale content production followed, including high-quality photography, videography, copywriting, and multimedia storytelling that captured the essence of the spa and

resonated with diverse audiences. A structured posting schedule and analytics tracking ensured consistency, optimal engagement, and data-driven adjustments. The revitalised social media presence contributed to a stronger brand identity and wider reach, leveraging influencer collaborations, customer testimonials, and targeted promotions. Interactive posts and inclusive visual storytelling helped establish the spa as a distinctive wellness destination in Slovenia. The project laid a solid foundation for future campaigns and sustained audience growth.

Team ID **8570350**

Challenge: Elevating Tower Spa's Brand Through Engaging Digital Content

Summary of Challenge: enhance the Tower Spa's digital presence and engagement on key social media platforms, including TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn

Short description of results: The team developed a strategic social media plan for a Tower Spa, grounded in market research and global wellness trends. By analysing top-performing private spas worldwide, they crafted a tailored content strategy focused on the spa's historical uniqueness, innovative wellness offerings, luxury appeal, and customer engagement. A structured content plan was implemented, incorporating high-quality multimedia elements such as photos, videos, testimonials, and storytelling posts. The second phase of the project emphasised inclusive representation, featuring a diverse model portfolio to position the spa as a welcoming, must-visit destination for tourists in Slovenia. Through strong visual branding and engaging calls to action, the team significantly improved the spa's online presence, strengthened its identity, and boosted audience interaction across social platforms.

Team ID **8700304**

Challenge: Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

Summary of Challenge: develop innovative strategies that combine photography, graphic design, video production, and content creation to craft cohesive marketing campaigns for natural skincare and luxury spa

Short description of results: The project focused on enhancing the B2B and brand marketing strategy for the company's skincare and spa services. The team conducted market research, identified qualified leads across Europe and the USA, and developed tailored cold email campaigns to initiate high-value business conversations. A comprehensive visual and content strategy was created to elevate the institute's online presence, combining aesthetic storytelling, engaging social media content, and science-based messaging. Deliverables included a content calendar, visual guidelines, and promotional concepts aligned with the institute's premium positioning. The team also

analysed the brand, website, competitor landscape, and past campaigns to propose actionable improvements, some of which have already been implemented by the company. Key contributions included visual mood board design, social media messaging strategies, and refinements to the customer journey. Collectively, these efforts led to improved lead generation and a more impactful digital presence.

Team ID **8730145**

Challenge: Marketing And Selling Campaigns Based On Market Research

Summary of Challenge: prepare effective selling and marketing strategies for managing gift cards in shopping centres

Short description of results: As part of the co-creation project, the team conducted market research across five countries and developed a detailed marketing strategy for one of them, namely, Saudi Arabia. The research identified strong potential for gift card solutions in the Baltic states and highlighted Saudi Arabia as a rapidly developing market with significant growth opportunities. The project included comparative analyses of shopping malls in various countries, marketing surveys, and the collection of contact information for key retail managers. Specific contributions included a focused marketing analysis of the Saudi market and detailed research on shopping malls in Finland. The team also prepared a strategic document outlining a country-specific pitch approach for Smartgiftly, designed to be adapted and replicated across different markets. This collaborative effort provides a valuable foundation for expanding the company's presence internationally through a scalable and informed marketing framework.

Team ID **8730292**

Challenge: Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

Summary of Challenge: to extend the open season of a restaurant beyond summer; to develop a marketing campaign focused on foreign tourists; highlight cultural, historical, and natural attractions

Short description of results: The team developed a targeted marketing campaign to promote tourism to a hospitality establishment in Harkány County in Hungary. Their work focused on business development strategies aimed at increasing regional visibility, attracting new visitors, and strengthening the destination's brand. Contributions included collaborative planning, market analysis, and campaign design tailored to the area's unique offerings.

Team ID **9090183**

Challenge: Unlocking Market Potential: Comprehensive Analysis of Healthy Ice Creams for the Health-Conscious Consumer

Summary of Challenge: conducting a comprehensive market analysis of healthy ice creams and related frozen desserts

Short description of results: The project offered valuable insights and high-quality data on the healthy ice cream market, with a focus on health-conscious consumers and inclusive, sustainable product development. The team conducted thorough market research, analysing consumer behaviour, regional trends, and opportunities for product positioning, particularly in European and Asian markets. Their data-driven approach led to strategic recommendations, including the use of functional and natural ingredients, personalised offerings, indulgent flavours, and a strong emphasis on transparency and sustainability. The project not only resulted in a strong branding approach that emphasised health benefits but also included the creation of targeted promotional content aligned with consumer values. One of the proposed innovations involved incorporating kefir as a superfood ingredient in future product lines.

Team ID **9200237**

Challenge: Forecasting and predicting customer's behaviour and their ability for repaying their obligations

Summary of Challenge: develop an innovative business model that incorporates financial and behavioural scoring to predict the ability of customers to meet their financial obligations

Short description of results: The team developed an initial predictive system for forecasting payment delays in the factoring finance sector, using historical financial and behavioural data from numerous companies. The model provides a foundational step toward a more refined solution for anticipating customer payment behaviour. Leveraging machine learning algorithms, the system transforms complex transactional and financial records into actionable forecasts, assessing both the likelihood and timing of delayed payments. Key components included automated data processing, predictive feature engineering, risk classification, and regression modelling. The model supports early identification of high-risk clients and offers structured evaluation reports that aid in financial risk management. Team contributions spanned exploratory data analysis, model development, feature engineering, and the creation of an implementation strategy. Collectively, the effort demonstrated the feasibility of applying AI-driven approaches to enhance cash flow forecasting and credit decision-making in the financial sector.

Team ID **9240150**

Challenge: Gaining Momentum Through Effective Marketing

Summary of Challenge: find a cost-effective marketing strategy for a wine production company that raises visibility and connects with target market

Short description of results: The project delivered a comprehensive and innovative marketing strategy aimed at increasing brand awareness and driving sales across both B2C and B2B segments. Clear, actionable solutions were presented across defined marketing areas, supported by practical guidelines for effective implementation. The outcome offers strong potential for business growth and long-term brand positioning. The team developed a creative, cost-effective approach combining digital engagement, experiential marketing, and strategic partnerships. For the B2C segment, the strategy integrated traditional advertising with influencer collaborations and event-based promotions to build loyalty and connect with niche audiences. For B2B, targeted initiatives included LinkedIn campaigns, airline onboard selling, and partnerships with vegan restaurants and the hospitality sector. Strategic analysis of competitor practices further reinforced the campaign's relevance and competitiveness. Together, these efforts positioned the brand as a premium and innovative product ready to expand its market presence.

Team ID **9340132**

Challenge: New Ideas To Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches

Summary of Challenge: revolutionising the company's approach to promoting advanced organic skincare

Short description of results: The project developed inclusive and innovative marketing strategies to promote the company's natural skincare products. The team produced in-depth market research, including analysis of spa and massage centre needs and competitor strategies, particularly in Slovenia. Emphasising accessibility and diversity, they created visual media content that reflects natural, health-conscious values for a global audience. Key outputs included an AI-generated transformation video and an educational piece on product benefits. The work addressed key industry challenges in the health and wellness sector with practical, impactful solutions tailored to market demands.

Team ID **9440173**

Challenge: Green Efficiency: Designing the Future Marketing Campaign for Connect IQ

Summary of Challenge: develop an innovative marketing campaign, focusing on promoting products for monitoring machine performance and energy consumption in industry

Short description of results: The project focused on identifying the right strategy to address the challenge, analysing competitors, particularly across Europe, and proposing a compelling digital marketing campaign. The team conducted detailed research on similar companies and their promotional tactics, aiming to highlight the unique benefits of the company's products through a targeted and effective online campaign.

Team ID **9510179**

Challenge: Young People Live Sustainably

Summary of Challenge: to develop a two-way communication campaign on living sustainably with a low income targeting children and young people

Short description of results: The team successfully developed and executed a social media campaign aimed at promoting access to quality education for underserved children through a digital platform that connects students with volunteer tutors. The campaign raised awareness across a broad international audience and was supported by a survey of over 100 stakeholders from various countries, generating valuable market insights for educational services contributing to sustainable development. The campaign strategy included clear milestones, task distribution, media planning, and targeted messaging to ensure effective outreach and engagement. Visual design, branding, and impactful presentations played a key role in building a recognisable and trustworthy image. The team also worked on features to help parents track student progress and results more effectively. Contributions included market analysis, persona development, feedback integration, and refining the campaign's direction based on public opinion. Additionally, a government relations (GR) component was introduced, focusing on connecting policymakers with end users and fostering a positive attitude among decision-makers toward inclusive education initiatives. The result was a comprehensive and collaborative effort that combined creativity, strategy, and advocacy to support global educational equity.

Team ID **9510233**

Challenge: Crack the code: Help us connect with the next gen of learners online

Summary of Challenge: map the digital landscape of where kids, parents, and teachers hang out online, and make learning as engaging as their favourite content

Short description of results: The team developed a creative educational campaign designed to make learning more engaging and accessible for young people. The concept centred around an inclusive digital platform, using TikTok and Instagram, where students create short, topic-based videos and participate in family challenges. This approach promotes creativity, collaboration, and learning through gamified rewards and social media integration. Comprehensive market and media research were conducted, including trend analysis and a stakeholder survey that provided key insights into the Slovenian education system and students' interests. The campaign also featured a strategic marketing plan aligned with the company's vision, focusing on accessibility, student motivation, and teacher involvement. Team members contributed across multiple areas: co-authoring the concept, creating teacher questionnaires, conducting media and trend research, preparing campaign reports, and coordinating communication. Strong leadership ensured smooth coordination, clear messaging, and stakeholder alignment. The result is a well-rounded and innovative approach to bridging educational gaps while inspiring active student participation.

Team ID **9550293**

Challenge: New sustainable service offerings in a family-owned restaurant

Summary of Challenge: develop new services for a restaurant, to enhance the dining experience, attract new customer segments, and modernise operations

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive strategy to modernise and enhance the services of a restaurant while preserving its rich culinary heritage. The project identified and analysed three key customer segments: international tourists, students and youth, and fast-food customers. For each group, tailored service models, digital solutions, and targeted marketing strategies were proposed to improve customer experience and engagement. Detailed personas and user journey maps were created to guide service development, along with practical recommendations such as multilingual menus, student discounts, and culturally immersive dining experiences. A specialised persona also captured the preferences of both traditional diners and modern fast-food enthusiasts. The Product Profile emphasised sustainability, featuring eco-friendly packaging made from biodegradable and recyclable materials. The proposed service innovation included a digital ordering app offering personalised meal options and a loyalty programme that rewards sustainable choices. Together, these materials provide a strategic foundation for enhancing customer satisfaction, expanding market reach, and aligning the restaurant's operations with modern expectations, while remaining true to its authentic culinary identity.

Team ID **9620176**

Challenge: Competitor Analysis of ClimateLaunchpad (EIT Climate-KIC)

Summary of Challenge: ClimateLaunchpad, the green business ideas competition, is undergoing a redesign to enhance its impact and reach; aim is to conduct a competitor analysis and identify best practices and opportunities for improvement

Short description of results: The Competitor Analysis that is the output of this project presents a comprehensive overview of sustainable innovation competitions worldwide, with a primary focus on ClimateLaunchpad, the world's largest green business ideas competition. The analysis categorises events by region (Europe, Asia-Pacific, Africa, and the Americas) and highlights key elements such as start-up maturity stages, innovation hotspots, and sustainability themes. The research draws on both primary and secondary sources, including stakeholder interviews and surveys, and outlines common challenges faced by participants, such as limited access to funding, mentorship, and networking opportunities. Based on these findings, the team proposed strategic improvements to enhance participant experience, including increased competition transparency and targeted support mechanisms. The project also offered actionable suggestions for expanding ClimateLaunchpad's offerings, tailored to trends observed across similar global initiatives. Contributions included coordinating communication with stakeholders, supporting survey development, gathering comparative data on similar programmes, and managing project timelines and team responsibilities. The result is a valuable resource that supports strategic planning for the continued evolution of ClimateLaunchpad and similar sustainable innovation platforms.

Team ID **9650145**

Challenge: Marketing And Selling Campaigns Based On Market Research

Summary of Challenge: prepare effective selling and marketing strategies for managing gift cards in shopping centres

Short description of results: The team conducted a project focused on researching gift card solutions for shopping centres in North Macedonia, Serbia, and Poland. They identified and compiled key information on shopping centres into a structured Excel database, analysed competitors, and created a detailed comparative overview of the gift card market. Based on these insights, a contact strategy was developed, including outreach to shopping centres and acquisition of manager contact details. The team coordinated calls, gathered contacts, and forwarded them to relevant stakeholders for further engagement.

Team ID **9650247**

Challenge: Project Brief for IKEA: Future-Driven Market Insights for Furniture & Home Furnishing Accessories in Slovenia

Summary of Challenge: actionable insights into the Slovenian furniture market, understanding the competitive landscape, customer needs, and future purchasing trends in an omnichannel environment

Short description of results: In collaboration with the company, the team conducted a comprehensive analysis of the Slovenian furniture market, combining survey results with desk research. The project examined market structure, key competitors, consumer behaviour, and emerging shopping trends, with a particular focus on quality, sustainability, and omnichannel strategies. A consumer survey was designed and analysed to capture demographic and psychographic insights, revealing expectations around product quality, eco-consciousness, and the integration of online and offline retail experiences. In parallel, a competitive analysis explored the offerings and pricing strategies of both local and international players. The findings identified clear opportunities for the company to differentiate its market approach and strengthen its presence in Slovenia. The project not only supported strategic decision-making but also enhanced the team's skills in market research, data interpretation, and collaborative analysis.

Team ID **9670144**

Challenge: Project 3in1: Innovative Approaches to Discovering Consumer Needs. An In-Depth Detergent Market Overview and Trend Analysis

Summary of Challenge: market analysis, identify and understand consumer needs in laundry detergent consumption

Short description of results: The team conducted in-depth research on the liquid detergent market in North Macedonia, Bulgaria, and Slovenia. They analysed market trends, competition, and industry positioning, supported by desk research on brands, social media presence, and consumer behaviour. Online surveys were developed to explore laundry habits, detergent preferences, pricing sensitivity, and shopping routines. The findings provided valuable insights into consumer values and pain points, offering the company strategic guidance and identifying key opportunities for a successful product launch.

Team ID **10030313**

Challenge: Illuminating the Invisible: UV-visible Marking on Recycled Paper

Summary of Challenge: solution for marking recycled paper with UV-visible ink codes to enable automated quality control and product tracking

Short description of results: The team explored multiple innovative solutions for printing invisible barcodes on recycled paper, addressing the challenge from various angles. The research focused primarily on UV fluorescence-based marking, using inks that remain invisible under normal light but become visible under UV light, an effective and affordable approach for secure labelling. Additional methods were also examined, including thermochromic and magnetic inks, as well as nanotechnology-based solutions. After evaluating sustainability, cost-efficiency, and detection accuracy, UV-reactive inks were identified as the most viable option. The team tested different fluorescent compounds, assessed readability on recycled substrates, and optimised printing techniques to improve scan reliability, especially under high-speed production conditions.

Team ID **10360348**

Challenge: Innovative Skincare Formulation: Advanced Research and Optimization

Summary of Challenge: refine skincare formulations by improving ingredient synergy, optimising delivery strategies, and implementing advanced analytical techniques; explore multi-component absorption, refine formulation compositions, develop new evaluation methods to ensure improved topical efficacy

Short description of results: The team contributed to the development of an innovative skincare product by integrating scientific research, market insights, and sustainability principles. Their work focused on optimising formulation parameters and selecting natural ingredients in line with clean beauty standards. A prototype transdermal gel incorporating fisetin-loaded ethosomes was successfully developed. In the laboratory, multiple ethosomal systems were formulated, with component ratios systematically adjusted to enhance performance. Key formulation aspects such as pH, texture, and stability were refined, alongside thoughtful choices of preservatives and packaging to ensure both efficacy and environmental responsibility. The project also included marketing support, with the creation of promotional videos and blog articles to build brand awareness and engage customers. By exploring advanced delivery systems and emphasising sustainable practices, the team laid a strong foundation for eco-friendly skincare solutions with commercial potential.

Team ID **10420201**

Challenge: Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations

Summary of Challenge: improve the body's ability to absorb fisetin, a flavonoid known for its anti-aging and anti-inflammatory properties

Short description of results: The team conducted in-depth research on five promising methods for encapsulating fisetin to enhance its bioavailability and absorption in the human body. They developed detailed preparation and analysis protocols for four of these methods, aiming to improve solubility and oral delivery. The primary focus was on nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), identified as a highly effective strategy for improving fisetin's solubility and bioavailability. In addition, team members explored alternative encapsulation techniques, including cyclodextrins, polymeric micelles, polymeric nanoparticles, nanoemulsions, and solid lipid nanoparticles. Each method was examined through comparative analysis of advantages and limitations, supported by theoretical experimental designs and product analysis. This comprehensive approach provided valuable insights into formulation strategies, offering a solid foundation for future development of fisetin-based supplements with enhanced therapeutic potential.

Team ID **10420311**

Challenge: Researching Innovative Approaches for Enhancing Skincare Formulation

Summary of Challenge: develop optimised skincare formulations that enhance topical efficacy; researching existing patents and products, investigating synergistic effects of various active ingredients; analysing formulation composition, evaluating delivery strategies, and utilising advanced analytical methods to determine multi-component absorption and penetration without conducting direct absorption testing

Short description of results: The team conducted extensive research into advanced skincare formulations, focusing on fisetin-loaded nanocarriers and innovative delivery systems such as ethosomes and gels. Their work explored strategies to enhance stability, bioavailability, and dermal absorption, addressing key technical challenges such as solubility and carrier selection. Through the review of over 18 scientific studies and patents, the team identified optimal formulation conditions offering the best performance for enhanced skin penetration and product stability. Regulatory considerations and patent potential were also evaluated, contributing to a well-rounded development roadmap. Contributions included analysing encapsulation techniques, interpreting research data, summarising regulatory insights, and drafting recommendations tailored to fisetin's properties. These efforts culminated in a clear and actionable presentation, providing valuable guidance for the development of stable, effective, and innovative skincare products.

Team ID **10550201**

Challenge: Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations

Summary of Challenge: improve the body's ability to absorb fisetin, a flavonoid known for its anti-aging and anti-inflammatory properties

Short description of results: The project yielded valuable research outcomes, including proposed combinations for tailored SNEDDS (Self-Nanoemulsifying Drug Delivery System) formulations designed to enhance fisetin's absorption and bioavailability. Drawing on established formulations developed for other drug compounds, the team conducted comprehensive literature reviews, extracted relevant data, and designed potential new formulations. In addition to formulation design, the team proposed analytical methods to assess absorption levels, providing a foundation for verifying the improved bioavailability of fisetin through these advanced delivery systems. These contributions offer a strong basis for further development and validation of fisetin-based SNEDDS formulations.

Team ID **10550311**

Challenge: Researching Innovative Approaches for Enhancing Skincare Formulation

Summary of Challenge: develop optimised skincare formulations that enhance topical efficacy; researching existing patents and products, investigating synergistic effects of various active ingredients; analysing formulation composition, evaluating delivery strategies, and utilising advanced analytical methods to determine multi-component absorption and penetration without conducting direct absorption testing

Short description of results: The project focused on enhancing fisetin's transdermal absorption and bioavailability through tailored formulations of ethosomes and transethosomes. Drawing from existing models and literature on similar drug compounds, the team designed and proposed advanced delivery systems supported by scientific data. Key outcomes included the development of potential formulation combinations and the suggestion of analytical methods to assess absorption efficiency. The results provide a strong foundation for further research and validation, with the aim of confirming improved fisetin bioavailability through the use of optimised nanocarrier systems and biopotentiators. This work contributes to the ongoing advancement of effective transdermal delivery solutions.

Team ID **10550349**

Challenge: Eco-Friendly Solvents for Cosmetics: Harnessing the Power of DES

Summary of Challenge: identifying the most effective solvent types for transdermal and topical applications, assessing their safety, and developing innovative formulations that outperform traditional solvents

Short description of results: The project focused on designing tailored formulations, such as ethosomes, transethosomes, and SNEDDS (Self-Nanoemulsifying Drug Delivery System), to enhance the absorption and bioavailability of fisetin for transdermal delivery. Drawing inspiration from formulations developed for other drug compounds, the team conducted a comprehensive literature review, extracted relevant data, and designed potential delivery systems. They also proposed analytical methods to assess absorption levels and validate the increased bioavailability achieved through these enhanced formulations. The work combined scientific research with principles of clean and sustainable beauty, contributing to the development of effective and eco-conscious skincare solutions.

Team ID **11300202**

Challenge: New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare

Summary of Challenge: develop marketing strategies in skincare industry; revolutionising promotion of advanced organic skincare

Short description of results: The team successfully enhanced the digital presence of the company's skincare brand through a cohesive and engaging marketing strategy. Key deliverables included informative blog content, customer surveys, and high-quality product photography, designed to educate consumers, boost engagement, and build brand trust. The project also emphasised inclusivity and reflected the brand's values through strong visual storytelling. Survey analysis provided valuable insights into customer preferences, informing tailored content and refining marketing efforts. A comprehensive PowerPoint presentation captured the strategy, combining blog ideas, visual assets, and audience research to showcase a clear digital identity and engagement approach. Each team member contributed across content development, survey design, visual coordination, and strategy presentation, resulting in increased online interaction and stronger brand recognition. The project not only supported growth in digital visibility but also laid a solid foundation for future brand expansion through data-driven and creative solutions.

Team ID **11300300**

Challenge: Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare

Summary of Challenge: innovative marketing strategies for social media in the oversaturated skincare industry

Short description of results: The project focused on promoting natural skincare through creative and educational digital strategies. The team enhanced brand visibility by producing engaging blog content, coordinating professional product photography, and maintaining visual consistency across social media channels. These efforts increased website traffic, boosted social media engagement, and strengthened the brand's online identity. Contributions included content strategy development, blog writing and editing, and overseeing photoshoots, resulting in improved audience trust and a clearer, more compelling digital presence.

Team ID **11430180**

Challenge: AEPAP: From Advanced Engineering Prototypes To Actual Production

Summary of Challenge: product ideas that leverage the expertise of a consortium of small and progressive companies specialising in advanced manufacturing, precision machining, mechatronics, engineering and aluminium die casting

Short description of results: The team developed a modular medical unit concept designed for rapid deployment in extreme environments and disaster zones. The project combined innovative materials research, structural design, and sustainability principles to deliver a versatile and practical virtual prototype. The proposed xMED unit features a hexagonal structure that enhances strength and modular connectivity, enabling the formation of larger field hospitals. It integrates advanced materials such as self-healing composites, fire-resistant panels, and thermally adaptive layers, ensuring durability, hygiene, and adaptability. Through collaborative brainstorming and structured development, the team addressed gaps in current deployable medical infrastructure. Contributions included material research, cost analysis, life cycle assessment, market analysis, and structural optimisation. The solution aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals and is under consideration for further prototyping in the next phase.

Team ID **11430230**

Challenge: Recycling 3D printing waste

Summary of Challenge: developing and testing processes to recover material from failed 3D prints and reprocess it

Short description of results: The team successfully developed a sustainable approach to recycling failed 3D prints into high-quality filament, contributing to a circular economy in the 3D printing industry. Addressing the growing issue of pre-consumer waste, particularly PLA print failures and production scraps, the project focused on creating a cost-effective, closed-loop system that retains the original material quality while transforming waste back into usable feedstock. Each team member actively contributed to different aspects of the project, from idea generation and technical development to environmental assessment. The solution was built on thorough material characterisation, enhancement of filament properties, and the design of an extrusion system tailored for recycled PLA. The project also included research on environmental regulations, life cycle assessment, and market analysis, ensuring the solution's feasibility and alignment with industry standards. This collaborative effort not only addressed a critical environmental challenge but also laid a practical foundation for scalable, circular manufacturing in the 3D printing sector.

Team ID **11430232**

Challenge: Post-production process automation: Designing a system for the automatic removal of supports and surface smoothing of 3D prints.

Summary of Challenge: designing an automated system aimed at streamlining the post-processing phase of 3D printing

Short description of results: The project focused on optimising the post-processing workflow of 3D-printed parts by developing an AI-driven, semi- or fully-automated system for support structure removal and surface refinement. The team proposed two scalable solutions: a fully automated but costly option, and a more affordable semi-automated alternative. A multi-modal approach combining robotics, machine learning, and intelligent control systems was implemented to identify surface defects and remove support structures efficiently. The team's contributions included developing the AI analysis pipeline, integrating it with robotic systems, and designing a scalable mechanical setup. Special attention was given to ensuring industrial feasibility, cost-effectiveness, and IoT connectivity. The final outcome is a technically robust and scalable concept ready for prototyping and future industrial application.

Team ID **11450150**

Challenge: Gaining Momentum Through Effective Marketing

Summary of Challenge: find a cost-effective marketing strategy for a wine production company that raises visibility and connects with target market

Short description of results: The project delivered a strategic overhaul of the company's marketing approach, offering fresh, actionable recommendations across all key channels. Through in-depth market and competitor analysis, including a comprehensive SWOT assessment, the team identified opportunities for differentiation and growth in a competitive landscape. The proposed marketing strategy is bold and trend-driven, placing emotional storytelling and relatable, inclusive content at its core. It aims to deepen audience connection by ensuring customers feel seen, inspired, and valued. Central to the plan is a visually compelling and interactive email campaign that reflects the brand's vibrant personality and delivers personalised content to drive loyalty and engagement. Additional recommendations focused on enhancing performance across social media, SEO, influencer partnerships, and paid ads. The team provided innovative content ideas, scripts for Instagram Reels, and targeted Meta ad copy. Research on industry leaders and evolving trends helped shape a unique brand identity, positioning the company as a standout in the wine sector. This collaborative effort has equipped the company with a refreshed perspective and a clear roadmap for sustainable growth, ensuring the company continues to evolve alongside shifting consumer needs while remaining true to its core values of quality, trust, and meaningful engagement.

Team ID **11450202**

Challenge: New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare

Summary of Challenge: develop marketing strategies in skincare industry; revolutionising promotion of advanced organic skincare

Short description of results: The project successfully elevated the company's skincare brand through an innovative and strategic marketing approach that blended current trends, personalised content, and powerful storytelling. The team conducted a thorough analysis of the brand, website, competition, and existing campaigns, identifying key areas for improvement and proposing actionable solutions, some of which have already been implemented by the company. By creating a dynamic brand voice and an interactive digital communication tool, the team enhanced customer engagement and loyalty. The customer journey was carefully designed to reflect the brand's values, offering a seamless experience with personalised recommendations and inspiring content. Creative initiatives, trend analysis, and a tailored social media and newsletter strategy positioned the brand as a distinctive and trusted name in the skincare market. These efforts laid a strong foundation for continued growth and long-term success.

Team ID **11450300**

Challenge: Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare

Summary of Challenge: innovative marketing strategies for social media in the oversaturated skincare industry

Short description of results: The team successfully enhanced the company's skincare brand through a strategic and data-driven marketing approach that combined current trends, personalised content, and compelling storytelling. A thorough competitor and brand analysis identified unique differentiators, strengthening the brand's market position and informing a clear, vibrant brand voice. Key outcomes included a dynamic digital communication platform, engaging newsletters, and SEO-optimised blog content, all designed to deepen customer connection, foster loyalty, and reflect the brand's core values. A seamless customer journey was crafted to provide tailored experiences and strengthen engagement at every touchpoint. Some proposed solutions have already been implemented by the company, validating the strategy's practical value. The project laid a solid foundation for continued growth and positioned the brand for long-term success in a competitive skincare market.

Team ID **11520209**

Challenge: Autonomous Roof Structure for Drone Hub

Summary of Challenge: Ensuring the safe and efficient operation of the company's hub's autonomous roof for drone landings and take-offs

Short description of results: The project focused on redesigning the company's hub's roof structure to ensure reliable drone operations under extreme weather conditions, particularly heavy rain and snowstorms. The solution involved two key components. First, the team developed an improved roof opening mechanism, exploring multiple design approaches, advanced materials, and product systems to enhance durability and functionality. The final design provides a solid foundation for future enhancements to the hub's structural resilience. Second, a comprehensive weather analysis was conducted, covering key regions in the UK, Austria, and Germany. Data from selected weather stations was used to identify environmental risks and develop climate-adaptive strategies that improve drone safety and operational reliability. This integrated approach, combining engineering innovation with real-time climate data, supports both technological advancement and environmental resilience in drone deployment.

Team ID **11520296**

Challenge: Airbridge Go To Market

Summary of Challenge: the company needs to better explain how its smart delivery centres help different businesses; their main challenge is showing customers and partners why their tech-powered delivery system is better than traditional methods

Short description of results: The project focused on developing a go-to-market strategy for the company's drone fleet management services in Slovenia. It explored the potential of drone delivery solutions across healthcare, service, and retail sectors, highlighting Slovenia's suitability as a pilot market due to its diverse terrain, compact geography, and openness to innovation. The team conducted in-depth market research, defined a phased market entry approach, and identified key opportunities for implementation. The resulting strategy offers a solid foundation for further development and scaling of drone-based logistics across Europe.

Team ID **11650300**

Challenge: Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare

Summary of Challenge: innovative marketing strategies for social media in the oversaturated skincare industry

Short description of results: The team developed a targeted B2B marketing strategy for the company, focusing on retailers, dermatologists, and spas. The strategy included a data-driven social media plan, email outreach campaigns, an influencer collaboration list, and website improvement suggestions. Professional content such as a whitepaper and blog post was also created to support brand positioning and international outreach. The social media strategy was built around competitive analysis, sustainable storytelling, and multimedia content ideas aimed at engaging eco-conscious European consumers. Visual content - photos, videos, and reels - was produced to enhance the brand's digital presence. Team contributions ranged from stakeholder coordination and task management to content creation and campaign execution. Outreach materials for doctors and retailers were designed, influencer-based content strategies proposed, and key blog topics, such as sun protection and the role of vitamins in cosmetics, were developed. Throughout the project, the team monitored engagement metrics and refined the strategy to align with the brand's values and performance goals, ensuring a cohesive and impactful marketing approach.

Team ID **11820179**

Challenge: Young People Live Sustainably

Summary of Challenge: develop a two-way communication campaign on living sustainably with a low income targeting children and young people

Short description of results: The project focused on encouraging young people to adopt more sustainable lifestyles by combining in-depth market and trend analysis with a dynamic two-way communication campaign. The team conducted a thorough analysis of target groups, comparable initiatives, and partner strengths and weaknesses, providing valuable insights to guide future collaborations. Based on the research findings, the team designed a creative and engaging marketing campaign aimed at connecting youth with political decision-makers and fostering their involvement in sustainability discussions. The campaign featured interactive elements, impactful hashtags, social media outreach, and partnerships with local organisations. Visual materials, including posters for street campaigns and short promotional videos, were developed to attract young audiences and inspire action. The outcome offers both strategic guidance for future initiatives and a replicable model for engaging youth in sustainable living. The comprehensive research and campaign design laid a strong foundation for deepening partnerships and launching meaningful, youth-focused sustainability efforts.

Team ID **11830289**

Challenge: Virtual Bar Caffè: Functional Development, Optimization and SEO Strategy

Summary of Challenge: for the virtual bar cafe, a virtual space for people to meet, in digital form; aim is to develop functionality implementation, platform optimisation and creating adequate SEO strategy to increase the visibility of the platform

Short description of results: The Virtual Bar Café project developed an innovative digital platform that merges social interaction with virtual technology, offering a dynamic alternative to traditional video calls. Key features include customisable spaces, themed rooms, chatbot integration, and built-in accessibility and inclusivity functions. SEO optimisation and user-centric design further enhance visibility and engagement. The project team contributed across multiple domains. Frontend developers built the platform using ReactJS and integrated WebRTC for real-time communication, while optimising system performance and security. Data analysts conducted in-depth trend analysis, developed predictive models, and created visualisations to guide feature refinement. Marketing and content specialists developed a conceptual framework, crafted engaging content, designed social media campaigns, and implemented SEO strategies to boost reach and user interaction. Together, these efforts resulted in a seamless, interactive, and inclusive virtual experience, positioning Virtual Bar Café as a distinctive platform for digital socialisation and community engagement.

Team ID **12120165**

Challenge: Water and Energy Saving in Aquatic Centres Facilities

Summary of Challenge: study of water and energy consumption in an aquatic centre facility and propose solutions to optimise the use of such resources

Short description of results: The project focused on improving water and energy efficiency at the CNAB Wellness aquatic facility in Barcelona through a comprehensive technical assessment. Key outcomes included identifying primary sources of energy and water consumption, evaluating inefficiencies in systems such as filtration, heating, and water distribution, and proposing actionable short-, medium-, and long-term solutions. The team developed a phased implementation roadmap supported by technical and economic feasibility analysis. Proposed upgrades, such as solar thermal panels, heat exchangers, automated backwashing, variable speed drives, smart sensors, and low-flow shower systems, are projected to reduce water consumption by 46% and energy use by 32%, resulting in significant cost savings and reduced emissions. Through benchmarking, data analysis, and collaborative research, the team identified core components of the solution and demonstrated the environmental and financial benefits of adopting sustainable technologies in water-intensive facilities.

Team ID **12140317**

Challenge: Innovative Marketing and Sales Campaigns of the Future for Horpol A. Horeczy Sp. K.

Summary of Challenge: redefine the company's approach to marketing, ensuring relevance and engagement; they are interested in developing creative solutions; effective differentiation in a saturated market, in the field of automotive lighting

Short description of results: The project delivered a comprehensive digital marketing brand and content strategy for the company, aimed at increasing visibility in key European markets and strengthening global outreach. The team developed a data-driven content calendar, email marketing framework, and competitor analysis, alongside strategic recommendations for audience engagement and multilingual content implementation. Key deliverables included audience personas, keyword strategy, visual branding guidelines, and paid ad concepts, all aligned with the company's commitment to innovation and customer-centric experiences. The work laid a strong foundation for consistent, scalable, and engaging marketing efforts across platforms, supporting the company's growth in an evolving automotive landscape.

Team ID **12190347**

Challenge: Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z"

Summary of Challenge: analyse students' and young adults' investment preferences; adapt existing products (at more applicable fees and other product flexibilities) and design an investment solution within company's regulatory restrictions

Short description of results: The project focused on understanding Generation Z's investment behaviour, financial literacy, and digital habits. The team conducted competitor analysis, reviewed existing investment products, and identified trends relevant to Gen Z. Based on these insights, they developed a concept for a modern, AI-assisted, and gamified investment app. Key features include interactive elements such as quizzes, a competition-based scoring system, a rewards page, a sales network section, and educational content. The app prototype, designed in Figma, features user avatars and an interface aligned with Gen Z aesthetics. The team also created an implementation plan, delivering a visually appealing and functionally robust product concept that provides valuable input for future development.

Team ID **12300190**

Challenge: Innovative Financial Health Reporting for Companies

Summary of Challenge: create a platform that generates a yearly and monthly financial health report for businesses

Short description of results: The result of the challenge is a web-based application designed to improve users' financial understanding by automatically generating comprehensive financial health reports. Based on input data, the platform highlights key metrics, trends, and areas for improvement in a clear and user-friendly format, empowering users to make informed financial decisions. The team developed the platform from concept to implementation, beginning with detailed designs in Figma and progressing to full development using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. Each development step was carefully documented, including formulas and feature descriptions to ensure transparency and ease of future updates. In addition to the technical work, the project included market research, visual content creation, and the design of interactive elements such as quizzes. The platform focuses on companies in Slovenia but is adaptable for broader use. The collaboration not only delivered a functional tool but also fostered strong teamwork and valuable connections.

Team ID **12310123**

Challenge: AI Avatar Interactive Learning System for Cutting-Edge EdTech Platform

Summary of Challenge: development of an AI Avatar framework, delivering real time responsive interactions with learners, to be integrated into educational platforms for 6–16-year-olds, featuring courses, interactive learning, gamification, AI assistance and analytics

Short description of results: The project focused on developing a functional prototype of an AI-driven EdTech platform featuring real-time user–AI interaction via voice and text on Mac/Linux PCs and Android devices. Grounded in a structured analysis of expert and user feedback on competing market solutions, the team defined key platform requirements and conceptualised an AI Avatar to enhance user engagement. A strategic and inclusive roadmap guided the implementation of core features, with special attention to psychological aspects of AI–user interaction and accessibility across platforms. The team conducted thorough market research, evaluated existing applications, and integrated feedback to shape the avatar’s behaviour and functionality. Contributions included system problem analysis, functional decomposition, AI Avatar design, task planning for the development team, prototype debugging in Python, and research into recognising psychological states through voice, gestures, and facial expressions. These efforts resulted in a stable prototype and a clear foundation for further development of an inclusive and adaptive EdTech solution.

Team ID **12450235**

Challenge: Innovative Biocomposite Product Using Industrial Hemp Fibers for High-Value Sustainable Applications

Summary of Challenge: development of a scalable, high-value biocomposite product made from industrial hemp fibres

Short description of results: The project explored the potential of industrial hemp in sustainable materials, resulting in three innovative biocomposite prototypes made from hemp fibres combined with PHB, PLA, and recycled PP. These materials targeted high mechanical performance, biodegradability, and commercial viability in packaging, construction, automotive, and consumer goods sectors. The team applied a structured innovation process, including market research, product ideation, SWOT analysis, prototyping, and utility evaluation. Their work ensured alignment with sustainable chemical technologies, with specific contributions focused on feasibility assessments, product property matrices, and prototype classification. The outcome provided strategic insights into the adoption of hemp-based biocomposites as viable alternatives to traditional plastics.

Team ID **12540179**

Challenge: Young People Live Sustainably

Summary of Challenge: to develop a two-way communication campaign on living sustainably with a low-income targeting children and young people

Short description of results: The project team developed a two-way communication campaign aimed at engaging youth (ages 8–24) in Utrecht, particularly from low-income backgrounds, in sustainable living. The campaign, titled »Our Future, Our Voice, Our Utrecht«, introduced six creative initiatives, such as Utrecht Green Graffiti Walls and Eco-Challenge Boxes, to connect young voices with policymakers and stimulate long-term civic participation. The approach included phased activities: idea generation, dialogue forums, and sustained engagement through digital platforms and gamification. The campaign drew from successful examples in other countries, placing local activities in an international context and ensuring relevance to diverse youth segments. The team conducted in-depth market research to identify engagement barriers and tailor inclusive messaging. Campaign strategies were co-developed to reflect youth preferences and sustainability goals, while evaluation metrics were designed to track impact and long-term effectiveness. Collectively, the project empowered young citizens, gathered actionable input for policy, and fostered a stronger connection between youth and decision-makers.

Team ID **12540240**

Challenge: Eco-Friendly Returnable Packaging

Summary of Challenge: design a durable, reusable packaging solution from leftover materials

Short description of results: The project developed three reusable packaging alternatives made from surplus materials, targeting the reduction of single-use cardboard in logistics. After a multi-criteria evaluation, the Modular Reusable Crate (MRC) was selected as the most effective solution, offering strong performance in cost-efficiency, operational integration, and environmental impact. The team created a virtual prototype of the MRC to showcase its durability and compatibility with existing logistics systems. Contributions included financial feasibility assessments, utility analysis, concept development, and documentation of the prototype.

Team ID **12600304**

Challenge: Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

Summary of Challenge: develop innovative strategies that combine photography, graphic design, video production, and content creation to craft cohesive marketing campaigns for natural skincare and luxury spa

Short description of results: The team played a key role in enhancing the visibility of the company's skincare and spa brand by developing a creative marketing strategy rooted in current trends, personalised content, and innovative digital tools. Their efforts improved brand differentiation, increased customer engagement, and laid a strong foundation for future growth. The project involved a clear division of tasks, including the creation of a chatbot for customer interaction, AI-generated videos using real imagery, and short blog posts to support SEO and brand storytelling. The visual and content strategy was designed to strengthen digital presence, combining engaging social media posts, optimised website content, and blog materials that reflected the brand's identity and values. While there is room for further development, the project met expectations and provided valuable insights for ongoing marketing initiatives. Through collaboration, creative execution, and digital innovation, the team delivered an impactful outcome that supports long-term brand evolution.

Team ID **12640301**

Challenge: Innovative B2B Solutions Through Cross-Industry Collaboration Challenge

Summary of Challenge: develop product ideas or business challenges within the B2B segment, and within web development with focus on AI and automation

Short description of results: The team collaborated with the company to develop innovative B2B concepts by leveraging the AI-Driven Circularity Manager (AICM) platform. Focusing on sustainability and cross-industry collaboration, they proposed three conceptual solutions: the Industrial Surplus Exchange Manager, the Sustainable Procurement Assistant, and the Carbon Collaboration Platform. Each tool utilises AICM's core components, such as AI classification, matching algorithms, compliance checks, and analytics, to address emerging challenges in circular economy and digital transformation. The ideas were assessed through a structured utility analysis, examining their technological feasibility, market relevance, innovation value, and environmental impact. Visual prototypes were created to communicate the core functions and user experiences of the proposed solutions. The result is a strategic set of B2B tools aimed at enhancing resource efficiency, meeting ESG goals, and enabling smarter, AI-supported industry practices.

Team ID **12670179**

Challenge: Young People Live Sustainably

Summary of Challenge: to develop a two-way communication campaign on living sustainably with a low-income targeting children and young people

Short description of results: The project “My Sustainable Utrecht” engaged local youth (ages 18–28) in civic participation through a co-created pilot initiative promoting sustainability. The team developed a virtual mini-election where young participants proposed and voted on ideas related to clean mobility, healthy food systems, circular economy, green public spaces, access to culture, and educational equity. These ideas were compiled into a Youth Sustainability Mandate, shared with policymakers and the public. The initiative included real-world workshops and digital tools to ensure inclusive access and democratic engagement. A detailed event framework was prepared, covering stakeholder engagement, partner/resource mapping (e.g., AllOne, Utrecht Duurzaam, INDUSAC, Topia), and a proposed timeline. Planning also extended to a future EU-level festival (via ECIU), featuring interactive installations, youth-led activities, and a social media countdown campaign. The team contributed to workshop design, content creation, inclusivity measures, and coordinated communication efforts in collaboration with youth ambassadors and local organisations.

Team ID **12670227**

Challenge: Educational Center at Greenagro

Summary of Challenge: create an educational programme for the company’s new educational centre

Short description of results: The project involved the creation of modern, interactive educational websites and materials designed to communicate complex topics in a simple, visual, and accessible way. The team developed platforms on topics such as machine learning and poultry farming with antibiotic awareness, tailored to diverse audiences including children and beginners. Features included quizzes, hands-on exercises, engaging visuals, and scientifically accurate content. Contributions spanned content research, text writing, presentation design, and both frontend and backend development. The results stood out for their creativity, adaptability, and commitment to fostering digital literacy and responsible learning across age groups.

Team ID **12670240**

Challenge: Eco-Friendly Returnable Packaging

Summary of Challenge: design a durable, reusable packaging solution from leftover materials

Short description of results: The project focused on designing sustainable, reusable packaging solutions for the company as an alternative to disposable cardboard, in line with circular economy principles. The team proposed four innovative concepts: recycled plastic crates, bioplastic-based boxes, upcycled soft carriers, and a smart modular system with RFID tracking. Following a structured evaluation process, the RFID-enabled modular system was selected as the most effective solution due to its durability, real-time tracking capability, and potential to enhance customer engagement. It aligns with the company's long-term strategy to lead in circular logistics and sustainable innovation. The team's contributions included research into solution viability, development of evaluation criteria, feasibility assessment, and final design preparation. They also supported the creation of a conceptual prototype and formulated sustainability and customer incentive features to strengthen the proposal.

Team ID **12980226**

Challenge: Internationalisation of Greenagro products and services

Summary of Challenge: introduce and expand the reach of the company's products in the international market

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive marketing strategy to support the company's international growth, with a focus on probiotic-based solutions in animal nutrition. The approach was grounded in customer surveys, competitor benchmarking, and trend analysis, particularly regarding the adoption of probiotics and feed additives in farming. Key deliverables included a refined brand positioning strategy, basic SEO improvements, and actionable content for digital channels such as Instagram and Facebook. Special emphasis was placed on boosting the company's online presence and credibility through targeted messaging aligned with scientific research and industry trends. The team also created a series of social media posts and visual assets to communicate the company's values and product benefits more effectively. Contributions spanned survey design, marketing research, trend analysis, content creation, and the proposal of a digital strategy tailored for B2B expansion beyond the Macedonian market.

Team ID **12980294**

Challenge: Developing Sustainable Event Services and Methodology for Restaurants

Summary of Challenge: to design a comprehensive sustainable event organisation service tailored for restaurants; create a methodology and practical guides that emphasise eco-friendly practices, efficiency, and customer satisfaction

Short description of results: The project aimed to help a restaurant attract a younger audience (ages 27–33) by blending tradition with a fresh, modern dining experience. The team proposed innovative concepts such as the “Hungarian Memory Plate” and the “Taste the Region” farm-to-table dinner series to strengthen emotional and local connections with guests. Additional ideas included brunches combining old and new recipes, cooking workshops in the garden, and digital tools for streamlined reservations. A comprehensive marketing strategy was developed, including partnerships with local businesses. The team conducted an in-depth analysis of the restaurant’s operations, customer base, and market position, resulting in a detailed company profile outlining strengths and opportunities in marketing, menu design, and digital engagement. Together, they also brainstormed actionable solutions to increase visibility and attract new clientele.

Team ID **13380231**

Challenge: Bioprinting - future technology for tissues and drugs

Summary of Challenge: improving the viability of cells during the 3D printing process

Short description of results: The team conducted a comprehensive exploration of bioprinting applications in regenerative medicine, with a focus on early-stage concepts and emerging technologies. The project addressed a range of innovative ideas, including PET calibration phantoms using two-photon polymerisation (2PP), bioprinted organ microvessels, cell scaffolds, drug- or cell-coated vascular stents, living drug factories, micro-scale synthesis devices, integration with ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC), and the development of ultra-thin syringe needles. In collaboration with an industry partner, the team reviewed existing bioprinting techniques, evaluating their principles, costs, advantages, and limitations. Based on this analysis, they proposed novel implementations, particularly in drug delivery and tissue engineering. Special attention was given to the feasibility of printing tissue scaffolds and vascular structures, including the selection of materials, production scalability, and mechanical stability. The project also included a structural and mechanical feasibility assessment of key components, such as syringe elements and stents, identifying appropriate technologies for precise and reliable fabrication. The team produced detailed reviews and recommendations that support future development in bioprinting for healthcare applications.

Team ID **13390235**

Challenge: Innovative Biocomposite Product Using Industrial Hemp Fibers for High-Value Sustainable Applications

Summary of Challenge: development of a scalable, high-value biocomposite product made from industrial hemp fibres

Short description of results: The project explored the use of biodegradable, thermoformable biocomposite materials made from industrial hemp fibre granules, free of chemical binders, for sustainable interior furniture applications. The team developed several functional prototypes, including chairs, cabinets, tables, plates, and decorative items, demonstrating the material's versatility and potential for eco-conscious design. Material testing showed promising results: the composite could be shaped at 180–185°C and maintained structural integrity upon cooling. Its simplicity, durability, and suitability for small-scale production made it a strong candidate for low-impact manufacturing. The furniture designs highlighted the natural hemp texture while integrating cost-effective construction elements, achieving a recognisable aesthetic and affordability. Contributions included material behaviour analysis, thermal testing, shaping and rendering of prototypes, waterproofing evaluations, and identification of manufacturing improvements such as tooling precision. The team also created supporting documentation and visuals, and coordinated with industry partners to align the concept with practical needs. Overall, the project provided technical innovation alongside real-world experience in design, collaboration, and sustainable product development.

Team ID **13560109**

Challenge: Development Of A Chlorine-Free Water Disinfection System

Summary of Challenge: develop cheap and easy-to-use method of disinfecting water beyond chlorine

Short description of results: The project introduces a Hybrid Bioaugmentation-UV Water Purification System as a sustainable, chlorine-free solution for providing clean drinking water in Poland. This innovative approach combines natural microbial degradation with UV disinfection, aiming to meet EU Directive 2020/2184 standards while enhancing water taste for a broad range of users. Comprehensive research, literature reviews, and marketing strategies have been completed, with future pilot testing planned among urban households, restaurants, and NGOs to assess feasibility and user satisfaction. The team collaboratively developed all project deliverables under coordinated leadership, ensuring alignment with public health and sustainability goals and laying the foundation for real-world validation.

Team ID **13590304**

Challenge: Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

Summary of Challenge: develop innovative strategies that combine photography, graphic design, video production, and content creation to craft cohesive marketing campaigns for natural skincare and luxury spa

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive visual and content strategy to strengthen the digital presence of the company, aligning it with the brand's eco-luxury identity. Based on detailed audience analysis across gender and age groups, they produced targeted SEO-optimised blogs, professional product visuals, social media reels, and promotional materials to boost engagement and brand visibility. The project included a refined brand presentation, influencer research, and the identification of AI tools to support future content creation. Market segmentation insights informed the tone and topics of six in-depth blog articles, each tailored to resonate with the brand's diverse customer base. Team contributions spanned market research, content creation, visual design, and strategy alignment, resulting in a cohesive, engaging digital presence and a stronger connection between the brand and its online audience.

Team ID **13620214**

Challenge: Educational LinkedIn Campaign: Recycling Facts, Myths, and Proper Waste Sorting Practices

Summary of Challenge: create a comprehensive LinkedIn educational campaign focused on promoting accurate recycling information, debunking myths, and explaining effective waste sorting practices

Short description of results: The project combined two campaigns aimed at enhancing digital engagement and educational impact. The first was a student-led online marketing initiative designed to engage younger audiences through peer-to-peer learning. Participants created short, explanatory videos on school-related topics, which were shared across digital platforms and promoted through a competition format with audience voting. This gamified approach fostered relatability, encouraged knowledge-sharing, and expanded brand visibility among a typically hard-to-reach demographic. The second campaign focused on strengthening the company's sustainability messaging and boosting customer engagement. The team developed over 10 editable social media graphics, including polls, educational carousels, and visuals on recycling and colour formulation, supported by tailored captions, hashtags, and a posting timeline. All materials were created in line with the company's branding, refined based on client feedback, and aligned with its environmentally responsible identity. Contributions included content analysis, visual and copy development, marketing strategy input, and final campaign documentation.

Team ID **13640179**

Challenge: Young People Live Sustainably

Summary of Challenge: to develop a two-way communication campaign on living sustainably with a low-income targeting children and young people

Short description of results: The project aimed to inspire young people to adopt environmentally friendly habits through a creative, youth-led Instagram campaign. The team reviewed sustainable youth initiatives in Thailand, the Philippines, and Brazil, and designed an international strategy to amplify green stories from around the world. Through a mix of educational and visually engaging content, such as feed posts and story templates, the campaign showcased practical, youth-driven responses to climate and environmental challenges. The team led campaign strategy, content creation, and community engagement, while also partnering with international organisations to align messaging and expand global outreach. The result was a relatable and inclusive campaign that encouraged sustainable living in everyday contexts and reached diverse youth audiences worldwide.

Team ID **13680258**

Challenge: BossFacade-EcoFacade

Summary of Challenge: physicochemical analysis of potential substitutions to existing materials for facades

Short description of results: The team evaluated the potential of pyrophyllite, an aluminosilicate ore with over 38 million tonnes available in the Konjic municipality, for use in modern eco-friendly façades in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The team investigated pyrophyllite's suitability as a value-added material through a series of physico-chemical analyses. Using samples from the region, they conducted structural (XRD), morphological (SEM), and suspension stability (zeta potential) studies. Special focus was given to acid-treated pyrophyllite, which revealed the presence of titanium nanoparticles, confirmed through XRD, suggesting potential catalytic properties in air purification. Thermal and acid modifications enhanced the material's characteristics. BET analysis showed a doubled specific surface area while retaining non-porosity, beneficial for mould prevention. Zeta potential tests demonstrated stable suspensions at alkaline pH (~9.22), supporting its practical use in façade applications. The team's interdisciplinary approach resulted in a promising pathway toward industrial pilot-scale development. The findings suggest that pyrophyllite can serve not only as a filler in eco-façades but may also offer functional benefits like pollutant degradation.

Team ID **13680345**

Challenge: Microelectronic Industry PCB boards recycling (PCB-REC)

Summary of Challenge: recycle electronic waste but also invest in innovative solutions beyond conventional e-waste recycling, such as gold or platinum extraction

Short description of results: The PCB REC project developed a practical and eco-friendly method for recycling microelectronic waste, recovering up to 30% copper per gram of printed circuit board (PCB) material. The process also enabled the synthesis of high-quality copper oxide (CuO) nanoparticles, valued for their catalytic and antibacterial properties. Combining hydrometallurgical extraction and nanoparticle synthesis in a scalable workflow, the project supports circular economy principles and urban mining efforts. The research was divided into three phases: preparation of PCB-derived starting material, CuO nanoparticle synthesis, and product characterisation. The resulting nanoparticles were analysed using FTIR, XRD, and SEM techniques to confirm surface functionality, crystalline structure, and morphology. This approach offers both environmental and economic benefits while avoiding the disclosure of proprietary details. Team members contributed to analytical work, including SEM and XRD measurements, as well as the interpretation of data, highlighting the project's relevance in sustainable nanomaterial development.

Team ID **13830312**

Challenge: Croatian market research regarding the sale of concrete products

Summary of Challenge: research on the Croatian market along the Slovenian border (border counties); Croatian market research regarding the sale of concrete products (pavers, curbs, bricks, slabs,...) for entry into the Croatian market

Short description of results: The project delivered a detailed market analysis to support the company's expansion into the Croatian market. The team identified key distributors, potential customers, and major competitors in Croatian counties bordering Slovenia. The analysis included pricing trends, sales volumes, discount strategies, and regional market dynamics within the concrete products sector. Research also covered online sales conditions, such as shipping fees, return policies, and ordering terms, and incorporated a comprehensive SWOT analysis to inform a tailored marketing campaign. Contributions included targeted market research, competitive benchmarking, campaign adaptation, and preparation of actionable insights. The results provide a strategic foundation for informed cross-border business development.

Team ID **13830329**

Challenge: Constructing a Creative Marketing Campaign to Attract Macedonian Generation Z Investors in Financial Services

Summary of Challenge: innovative, strong and research-backed digital and offline marketing campaign to attract Macedonian generation Z investors

Short description of results: The project delivered a comprehensive digital marketing strategy aimed at engaging generation Z in North Macedonia, with a focus on platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. Following in-depth market research, trend analysis, and competitor benchmarking, the team developed a content arsenal that included posts, reels, a yearly content calendar, and automation proposals. The strategy emphasised Gen Z's digital behaviour, ESG values, and preference for gamified, visual learning, resulting in a proposed campaign titled "Invest Smart, Start Small." Key outputs included ready-to-post content, platform feature recommendations, and a strategic positioning framework for Capital Asset Management's micro-investment product. The project supported the company's goal to attract a younger, digitally engaged client base, offering a clear communication approach rooted in current marketing trends.

Team ID **13830347**

Challenge: Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z"

Summary of Challenge: analyse students' and young adults' investment preferences; adapt existing products (at more applicable fees and other product flexibilities) and design an investment solution within company's regulatory restrictions

Short description of results: The team developed a concept for a mobile investment app tailored to Generation Z, integrating gamification, educational content, and AI-powered support to enhance financial literacy and engagement. Designed to encourage small, regular investments, the platform aims to make investing simple, accessible, and rewarding for young users. A persona analysis was conducted to inform product development and ensure alignment with Gen Z habits and preferences. The solution emphasises inclusivity and interactivity, combining intuitive design with features that empower users to learn and invest simultaneously. While some aspects of the app remain confidential due to market competition, the overall approach demonstrated a well-researched and innovative response to the needs of younger investors.

Team ID **13930233**

Challenge: Crack the code: Help us connect with the next gen of learners online

Summary of Challenge: map the digital landscape of where kids, parents, and teachers hang out online, and make learning as engaging as their favourite content

Short description of results: The project aimed to effectively engage younger audiences by leveraging platforms such as TikTok and Instagram. Through detailed persona analysis, the team identified content preferences, behaviours, and communication styles within the target demographic. This informed a tailored digital strategy designed to drive active participation and increase resonance with younger users. The first phase focused on market and company research, while the second included concrete, actionable deliverables for a future marketing campaign. These encompassed trend analysis, persona creation, campaign purpose definition, and visual brainstorming materials.

Team ID **13980169**

Challenge: Business plan for a digital tool on healthy urban planning

Summary of Challenge: perform market research and develop a business plan for a digital tool designed to empower city planners, policymakers, and community stakeholders to create healthier cities by providing recommendations and insights into their health and economic impact.

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive business plan for the Healthy Cities Generator (HCG)—a digital tool designed to support health-informed urban planning. Their work included in-depth market research across several national markets, competitor benchmarking, and a user needs analysis to define key functionalities and market positioning. The business model was structured using tools such as the Business Model Canvas, SWOT analysis, and Value Proposition Canvas, with specific attention given to pricing strategies, customer segmentation, and channel selection. The team proposed revenue-enhancing pricing models, including modular add-ons, consortium licensing, and per-project pricing. Deliverables included a full business plan, executive summary, sales and legal strategy, competitor analysis, and optional pricing models. Contributions were distributed across market research, profitability estimation, strategic planning, and communication with company representatives to ensure alignment with real-world needs. The project not only produced actionable business strategies but also demonstrated the viability of HCG in an increasingly health-focused urban planning landscape.

Team ID **14010247**

Challenge: Project Brief for IKEA: Future-Driven Market Insights for Furniture & Home Furnishing Accessories in Slovenia

Summary of Challenge: actionable insights into the Slovenian furniture market, understanding the competitive landscape, customer needs, and future purchasing trends in an omnichannel environment

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive market analysis and strategic proposal for the company, addressing customer behaviour, digital experiences, and future product development. Research included a survey of 32 participants, interviews, online review analysis, and competitor benchmarking. Findings emphasised the need to improve online shopping experiences, enhance personalisation, and better communicate sustainability efforts. Key outputs included a SWOT analysis, trend mapping, and strategic recommendations aligned with the company's long-term goals. The team also produced structured data visualisations and user-centred insights to inform decision-making. Contributions spanned survey design, customer interviews, review aggregation, and the development of a future-oriented product feature catalogue. Overall, the project provided actionable strategies to strengthen the project's position in the Slovenian market while supporting innovation and customer engagement.

Team ID **14030179**

Challenge: Young People Live Sustainably

Summary of Challenge: develop a two-way communication campaign on living sustainably with a low income targeting children and young people

Short description of results: The project explored how local governments in different cities support young people in adopting more sustainable lifestyles, with a focus on mobility and urban cycling. The team compared municipal policies and cycling environments across various locations, gathering insights through surveys and direct communication with city councils. Young citizens were asked to evaluate their cities' efforts in promoting sustainable living, particularly in areas such as transport, infrastructure, and youth engagement. Field research in cities like Madrid and Castellón provided perspectives on both the challenges and opportunities faced by youth in transitioning toward greener lifestyles. Based on the findings, the team proposed policy recommendations aimed at improving municipal support for sustainable urban living.

Team ID **14030208**

Challenge: Enhancing digital marketing of a small International Fiscal & Law Firm

Summary of Challenge: increase the leads generation through comprehensive digital marketing plan, focused on SEO and SEM campaigns

Short description of results: The team delivered a comprehensive marketing strategy for a fiscal legal firm, aimed at positioning it as a trusted expert in cross-border tax law. The project included the development of ten practical, multilingual blog articles tailored to expatriates in Spain, offering clear guidance on legal and administrative matters such as taxation, healthcare, and residency. These resources were designed to make complex topics more accessible and improve the onboarding experience for international residents. The marketing strategy emphasised digital channels and targeted outreach to maximise visibility and engagement. Contributions included legal research, regulatory analysis, content development, and the creation of a culturally relevant communication plan. Strong collaboration between the team and the company allowed the project to be completed ahead of schedule.

Team ID **14030341**

Challenge: Creating Large-Scale Databases of Tool Companies, Wholesalers, Stores, and Garden Centers in Europe, the Middle East, and Asia, Along with Decision-Maker Identification and B2B Customer Segmentation

Summary of Challenge: developing a comprehensive database of tool companies, wholesalers, stores, and garden centres across Europe, the Middle East, and Asia, identifying key decision-makers responsible for procurement, and creating a B2B customer segmentation system

Short description of results: The team developed a proof-of-concept architectural design for a software engineering system tailored to the company's needs. Initial data was manually scraped from key sources to support system functionality. Alongside technical development, regulatory analysis was conducted to ensure compliance with data protection laws and international business standards. Outreach messaging was designed to be both culturally appropriate and legally compliant across jurisdictions. The team leveraged expertise in international law and cross-border communication to enhance the system's global applicability and readiness for international expansion.

Team ID **14130199**

Challenge: Shaping the Future of Machine Efficiency: Understanding Customer Needs for OEE Optimization

Summary of Challenge: develop a future-oriented approach to understanding customer needs and expectations for services that improve Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE)

Short description of results: The team developed a scalable digital platform concept for real-time OEE monitoring, predictive maintenance, and AI-driven performance optimisation tailored to manufacturing SMEs. Featuring a modular architecture, the solution ensures flexibility and seamless integration with existing systems, aiming to reduce downtime, enhance energy efficiency, and enable data-driven decision-making in emerging markets. As part of the project, the team conducted comprehensive market research, including PESTEL and competitor analyses, to assess adoption potential in Spain, Italy, and North Macedonia. This work informed the development of an innovation solution aligned with regional industrial needs. Contributions included feasibility assessments, platform development proposals, and the formulation of tailored go-to-market strategies to support successful market entry.

Team ID **14350355**

Challenge: Review of New Restrictions on Product Packaging and Labeling and Analysis of Impact on the Market

Summary of Challenge: conduct a complex review of new restrictions on product labelling and analyse their impact on the packaging and labelling market

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive, future-proof strategy to support the company in complying with evolving EU packaging and labelling regulations, particularly within the automotive industry. The solution integrates circular economy principles and includes recyclable and biodegradable materials, digital labelling technologies, and process optimisations to improve both environmental and cost efficiency. Key components included trend and scenario analysis, environmental and cost impact assessments, persona development, and evaluation of sustainable materials and technologies. The strategy aligns with directives such as the EU Circular Economy Directive and Single-Use Plastics Regulation. Contributions included regulatory analysis, product and persona profiling, concept ideation, and competitive benchmarking. The final proposal equips the company with actionable recommendations that enhance compliance, sustainability, and operational performance.

Team ID 14410293

Challenge: New sustainable service offerings in a family-owned restaurant

Summary of Challenge: develop new services for a restaurant, to enhance the dining experience, attract new customer segments, and modernise operations

Short description of results: The team proposed a new service and successfully developed an innovative solution aimed at improving workflow efficiency and data management for the client. The project included a comprehensive analysis of current processes, a set of tailored recommendations, and a prototype digital tool aligned with the client's specific needs.

Team ID 14410300

Challenge: Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare

Summary of Challenge: innovative marketing strategies for social media in the oversaturated skincare industry.

Short description of results: The team developed an inclusive and engaging digital marketing strategy for the company, with a focus on diversity, authenticity, and audience alignment. A curated list of nano-influencers was compiled to reflect a range of cultural backgrounds and personal styles, aligning with the brand's commitment to inclusivity. Social media templates and scripts were crafted using neutral, welcoming language to ensure broad accessibility and relatability. The project also delivered a complete set of personalised short-form video scripts for all 17 skincare products, designed to build trust, educate viewers, and reinforce brand identity. The scripts were carefully tailored to resonate with women aged 20–40, using subtle emotional appeal without sounding overly promotional. All content was approved for rollout, reinforcing the brand's tone and expectations. In addition, the team contributed to enhancing the company's digital presence by developing strategic content plans, analysing social media trends, and supporting improvements in visual identity across platforms. The overall approach strengthened the brand's online communication and engagement with its audience.

Team ID 14530179

Challenge: Young People Live Sustainably

Summary of Challenge: develop a two-way communication campaign on living sustainably with a low income targeting children and young people

Short description of results: The project focused on analysing and comparing two civic initiatives, Duurzaam Utrecht 2030 (Netherlands) and Legambiente Caserta (Italy), that

engage youth and local communities in sustainability through grassroots action. Both initiatives were evaluated using SWOT analyses to identify their strengths, challenges, and potential for collaboration. The team conducted a context analysis of Utrecht, referencing key frameworks such as the European Green Deal, Agenda 2030, and GreenComp. They assessed alignment with key Sustainable Development Goals, identified relevant local associations, and proposed opportunities for future partnerships. The comparison revealed complementary strengths: Duurzaam Utrecht excels in creative, participatory methods, while Legambiente Caserta offers a strong model of civic mobilisation and institutional cooperation. A strategic communication plan was developed to enhance visibility, community engagement, and scalability. The team designed the pilot campaign “Utrecht2030: Growing Together,” featuring participatory tools like environmental storytelling, sustainability passports, and direct youth-institution interactions. Team contributions included business model development, strategic communication, inclusive practice assessment, and the creation of reports and roadmaps to guide future cross-European collaboration.

Team ID **14540288**

Challenge: Energy-related regulation scenarios in Europe in 2030

Summary of Challenge: the company seeks insights on upcoming regulatory and policy changes in the European energy sector; analyse future market trends, emerging technologies, and strategies from leading energy companies across Europe; identify innovation streams to pursue

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive strategic innovation framework to support the company's transformation into a digital-first, client-centric energy service provider. Focusing on SMEs and industrial customers in Spain, the project introduced two modular service concepts: “Nexus Verde”, designed for small and medium-sized enterprises, and “Nexus360 Grid+”, tailored for industrial clients. Both solutions promote energy resilience, sustainability, and digital innovation. Key outputs included detailed client segmentation models, the development of service personas, and the design of digital onboarding tools. The team also created a clear roadmap for the integration of microgrids and active participation in flexibility markets. To ensure regulatory alignment and future-readiness, they produced a strategic plan addressing upcoming EU energy and digitalisation policies through 2030. Additional recommendations featured AI-based demand forecasting, real-time energy usage insights, and benchmarking strategies inspired by leading Nordic energy providers. The work positions the company to enhance operational efficiency, meet Green Deal objectives, and elevate customer engagement through advanced, scalable digital solutions.

Team ID **14640292**

Challenge: Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

Summary of Challenge: extend the open season of a restaurant beyond summer; develop a marketing campaign focused on foreign tourists; highlight cultural, historical, and natural attractions

Short description of results: The project delivered a comprehensive marketing strategy for a restaurant in Hungary, designed to strengthen its market position and attract both domestic guests and foreign tourists. The campaign included in-depth market and persona analysis, customer segmentation, trend forecasting, and three strategic development scenarios aligned with different innovation paths. These scenarios balanced traditional values with evolving customer expectations to ensure sustainable growth. The team proposed two detailed meal experience concepts to enhance customer engagement, brand image, and loyalty. External factors and emerging trends were carefully analysed to shape the campaign's strategic direction. Contributions also included synthesising research into clear, actionable marketing materials, ensuring the strategy was both practical and future-oriented.

Team ID **14640296**

Challenge: Airbridge Go To Market

Summary of Challenge: The company needs to better explain how their smart delivery centres help different businesses; their main challenge is showing customers and partners why their tech-powered delivery system is better than traditional methods

Short description of results: The team developed a targeted marketing campaign for a major British logistics company, focusing on drone transport solutions for healthcare providers in two UK regions. The project included in-depth market research, a comprehensive analysis of regional needs, and the creation of a tailored campaign strategy to promote the adoption of drone logistics in the healthcare sector.

Team ID **14700364**

Challenge: Creating a B2B Marketing Campaign for High-Quality decoration cosmetic packaging and plastic components various industries

Summary of Challenge: structured and organised approach to promoting the company's services decoration cosmetic packaging and plastic components in different industries

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive B2B marketing strategy for a company specialising in high-quality cosmetic packaging and plastic components. The project included competitor analysis, client segmentation, brand positioning, and tailored messaging to support international expansion. A detailed June content calendar was created, featuring LinkedIn post designs and captions to strengthen the company's digital presence. The team also proposed updates to tone of voice, visual identity, and overall brand strategy. Contributions spanned market research, content planning, and creative development, resulting in a clear roadmap for the company's growth in the European market.

Team ID **14880103**

Challenge: Innovative Custom-Made Hardwood Floors

Summary of Challenge: marketing approach for the launch of custom-made floors

Short description of results: The project centred on the creation and material development of the Essence Parquet Collection, a premium line of engineered wood flooring that blends traditional craftsmanship with modern aesthetics, sustainability, and surface innovation. The collection features advanced multi-layer structures, refined finishes, and contemporary interpretations of historical patterns drawn from Renaissance, Ottoman, and Balkan traditions. Emphasising local material sourcing, biophilic design, and aesthetic functionality, the project targets both residential and commercial applications. The team conducted detailed material analyses, focusing on oak and American walnut for their durability, visual appeal, and relevance to modern interior design. Historical and cultural research shaped the collection's design narrative, tracing the evolution of regional motifs and adapting them into elegant parquet patterns. Team contributions spanned from material evaluation and conceptual identity development to visual presentation strategies for web, social media, and promotional use, ensuring the collection communicates both its artisanal heritage and contemporary relevance.

Team ID **14880293**

Challenge: New sustainable service offerings in a family-owned restaurant

Summary of Challenge: develop new services for a restaurant, to enhance the dining experience, attract new customer segments, and modernise operations

Short description of results: The project aimed to strengthen the image of a restaurant, attract more tourists, and transform it into a year-round destination. It focused on improving marketing, digital presence, and guest experience through storytelling and integration of local culture. The interdisciplinary team proposed a three-part service concept: story-driven dining experiences, a smart service app, and eco-friendly practices with community

engagement. Together, these solutions support modernisation while preserving tradition and enhancing the restaurant's cultural identity. The team conducted research on current marketing efforts and recommended improvements, designing mock-ups, landing pages, and social media content to build a stronger online presence. Their work resulted in a forward-looking strategy that blends heritage with innovation to appeal to both local and international guests.

Team ID **15090306**

Challenge: AI-Powered EU Grant Advisory Platform Development for Scientific Innovations

Summary of Challenge: development of an AI-powered recommendation system using ComfyUI to guide scientists in identifying suitable EU funding opportunities for their deeptech innovations, integrated into a web-based platform

Short description of results: The team successfully developed and launched a fully functional AI-powered advisory platform tailored to support scientific innovators navigating the complexities of EU funding. The platform features three interactive chatrooms that guide users through fundraising, risk assessment, and impact evaluation, transforming these processes into intuitive, data-driven conversations. By integrating advanced analytical models such as KTH and Exponential Impact, the system delivers personalised reports and actionable strategic insights, significantly reducing barriers to EU grant access. The backend architecture includes a robust content retrieval engine, scoring algorithms, and automated report generation tools to ensure assessments are evidence-based and reliable. In parallel, the team designed a user-friendly interface with clear visual layouts and engaging conversational flows, making the platform accessible to a broad range of users. The seamless integration of language models and expert frameworks ensures that the user experience is both insightful and easy to navigate. This innovative tool empowers researchers and innovators with the knowledge and confidence to pursue funding, while enhancing the visibility and strategic alignment of their ideas within the EU's innovation ecosystem.

Team ID **15090307**

Challenge: Personalized Innovation Funding Alert System: Intelligent Newsletter Platform for Research Competitions

Summary of Challenge: creation of an intelligent newsletter service that aggregates and matches global innovation competitions, investment opportunities, and funding programmes with research teams based on their technology profile and growth objectives

Short description of results: Originally envisioned as a funding alert system, the project evolved into a more advanced platform: an Intelligent Technology Assessment & Innovation Benchmarking system. The tool delivers personalised newsletters that assess a researcher's technology by analysing scientific publications, patent databases, and EU project data. This insight enables innovators to evaluate the novelty and competitiveness of their work and align it with relevant funding and partnership opportunities. Accessible online, the platform supports researchers in strategically positioning their innovations for future development. Key technical components include a robust data scraping system designed to extract and structure information from diverse sources such as CORDIS reports, patent repositories, and peer-reviewed research databases. A secure and scalable subscription architecture enables differentiated access levels, while the platform's UI/UX design ensures a seamless user experience, from onboarding to digesting complex, data-driven insights. Together, these contributions form the operational, analytical, and visual backbone of a tool that empowers researchers to make informed, timely, and strategic innovation decisions.

Team ID **15090308**

Challenge: Innovation Ecosystem Matchmaking Platform: Expert-Innovator Connection Hub for Technology Commercialization

Summary of Challenge: development of an intelligent matchmaking platform that evaluates innovation readiness, identifies development gaps, and connects researchers with relevant domain experts while facilitating technology collaboration opportunities within specific sectors

Short description of results: The project delivered a sophisticated Fundraising and Partnership Newsletter Tool designed to support researchers in transitioning from innovation to commercialisation. The system automatically scrapes global funding databases and uses AI to score opportunities based on their relevance to a researcher's specific technology. It then generates a personalised newsletter with curated alerts for grants, competitions, and strategic partnerships. The team designed and implemented the entire system architecture, from the data pipeline and source scraping to the LLM-powered scoring and content generation engine. Python-based tools were developed to extract and structure data from platforms such as F6S, EU funding portals, and private investment databases, forming the foundation of the tool's real-time recommendation system. A user interface was also developed to present this complex data in a clear, actionable, and visually engaging newsletter format. Together, these efforts created a scalable, automated platform that enables researchers to identify relevant funding and partnership opportunities with ease and precision.

Team ID **15150255**

Challenge: Project Brief for IKEA: Designing the Marketing Campaign for Sustainability-Conscious Consumers

Summary of Challenge: designing an innovative and forward-thinking marketing campaign

Short description of results: The project focused on supporting the company in strengthening customer engagement with sustainable products and practices. Through consumer research, including focus groups, surveys, and persona development, the team explored how different generations in Slovenia perceive and act on sustainability. Findings highlighted that while both younger and older consumers are environmentally conscious, affordability remains a key decision factor. To address this, the team proposed strategies such as improved product labelling, targeted marketing campaigns, and services like furniture buy-back to encourage sustainable choices. They also developed detailed personas and realistic consumer scenarios to reflect customer motivations and challenges, using visual storytelling to enhance relatability.

Team ID **15220213**

Challenge: Digital Music Education Innovation

Summary of Challenge: innovative digital marketing strategies to promote an interactive classical music education platform

Short description of results: The project successfully delivered a comprehensive marketing and stakeholder engagement strategy for the Fortissimo digital platform, designed to make classical music education more accessible to children aged 6–14. The team developed a detailed stakeholder map and outreach plan, targeting schools, teachers, parents, and education ministries, with an initial focus on the German market. Strategic recommendations were made for partnership development, funding acquisition, and user feedback collection to support long-term adoption and scalability. The final handover included a clear, actionable roadmap based on extensive market and audience analysis.

Team ID **15220292**

Challenge: Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

Summary of Challenge: extend the open season of a restaurant beyond summer; develop a marketing campaign focused on foreign tourists; highlight cultural, historical, and natural attractions

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive marketing campaign to reposition a restaurant as a year-round cultural and culinary destination. The strategy targets broader audiences from neighbouring countries through digital storytelling, influencer collaborations, and multilingual content. On-site experiences, such as cooking workshops, QR-enhanced menus, and seasonal packages, were proposed to boost guest engagement and increase off-season visits. The campaign also reinforced partnerships with local institutions to support sustainable tourism and regional development. Team contributions included in-depth analysis, ideation of on-site and online campaign elements, and aligning hospitality-focused experiences with audience expectations.

Team ID **15230164**

Challenge: Office of the future: tech to wellbeing

Summary of Challenge: understand how SMEs see the 'office of the future' - which type of technological equipment should they contain; which equipment are they already using or planning to invest in and why

Short description of results: The team conducted a strategic SEO and competitor analysis to position the company in the evolving market of smart offices and future-oriented workspaces. The project combined Slovenian and English research to capture cross-market search behaviour, focusing on trends such as hybrid classrooms, ergonomic solutions, and energy-efficient technologies. Key activities included identifying customer-centric keywords, mapping SEO opportunities across the conversion funnel, and benchmarking competitor strategies. Behavioural clusters were developed based on innovation adoption and well-being focus, supporting segmentation and personalisation of future digital content. Additionally, the team proposed "WellSpace-as-a-Service," an integrated smart office subscription model tailored to SMEs, combining ergonomic technology, cloud-linked printing, and eco-conscious software. The insights shaped the company's positioning strategy, supporting content planning, subscription models, and user experience enhancements, all aligned with global digital competitiveness.

Team ID **15230341**

Challenge: Creating Large-Scale Databases of Tool Companies, Wholesalers, Stores, and Garden Centers in Europe, the Middle East, and Asia, Along with Decision-Maker Identification and B2B Customer Segmentation

Summary of Challenge: developing a comprehensive database of tool companies, wholesalers, stores, and garden centres across Europe, the Middle East, and Asia, identifying key decision-makers responsible for procurement, and creating a B2B customer segmentation system

Short description of results: The project delivered a comprehensive strategic package for the company, combining market intelligence with actionable business planning. Key outputs included a detailed user persona, a tailored business model, and the evaluation of three strategic alternatives, each assessed through a utility analysis to guide decision-making. To support data-driven strategies, the team developed a custom web scraping application using Python, Flask, and Selenium. This tool enables both targeted company data extraction and keyword-based market discovery, making it a valuable asset for lead generation and competitive analysis. Team contributions covered strategic planning, utility modelling, data collection, and team coordination, ensuring a structured and effective approach to the company's growth.

Team ID **15290164**

Challenge: Office of the future: tech to wellbeing

Summary of Challenge: understand how SMEs see the 'office of the future' - which type of technological equipment should they contain, which equipment are they already using or planning to invest in and why

Short description of results: The team conducted field research among SMEs in the Primorska region, Slovenia, to assess the demand for Smart Office solutions. Despite limited participation, they gathered valuable insights, which were shared with the company and used to shape potential product offerings. Based on the findings, five targeted research areas were explored: the application of AI in Smart Digital Archives, market analysis of digital poster solutions and available models, Smart Office trends and practices in Spain, and a comparative study of Ricoh and Epson technologies as possible additions to the company's portfolio. Additional supporting tasks were completed to enhance the overall recommendations and align them with the company's strategic direction.

Team ID **15290335**

Challenge: Hoply: Safe, and affordable rides for kids, simplifying after-school transportation for families

Summary of Challenge: developing a mobile app, ensuring a seamless platform registration for users, efficient scheduling and transport bookings, with secure and convenient payment system, enabling real-time transportation monitoring

Short description of results: The team successfully laid the foundation for the company's marketing programme, focusing on brand visibility, content creation, and partnership development. Tasks included establishing a social media presence, enhancing the official website, designing visual and video content, and conducting industry research. Promotional materials such as carousels, posters, flyers, and reels were created to support both online and offline outreach. Contributions also involved compiling strategic contact lists, drafting partnership guidelines, and mapping out local sports institutions for targeted engagement. The team coordinated interviews, filmed testimonials with company leadership, and edited content for social media campaigns. Leadership roles covered task distribution, deadline coordination, and strategic planning. The collaborative effort resulted in a scalable and engaging marketing operation that aligned with the company's growth objectives.

Team ID **15320176**

Challenge: Competitor Analysis of ClimateLaunchpad (EIT Climate-KIC)

Summary of Challenge: ClimateLaunchpad, the green business ideas competition, is undergoing a redesign to enhance its impact and reach; aim is to conduct a competitor analysis and identify best practices and opportunities for improvement

Short description of results: The team conducted a comprehensive benchmark analysis of Climate Launchpad and its global competitors supporting climate innovation start-ups. The research identified significant gaps in regional presence, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa, Southeast Asia, and Latin America, and emphasised Climate Launchpad's distinctive focus on the ideation stage. The analysis included both data and quantitative methods, leading to strategic recommendations aimed at expanding outreach, strengthening alumni engagement, and increasing the adoption of digital tools.

Team ID **15380292**

Challenge: Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

Summary of Challenge: extend the open season of a restaurant beyond summer; develop a marketing campaign focused on foreign tourists; highlight cultural, historical, and natural attractions

Short description of results: The team successfully delivered innovative solutions across distinct projects, each aimed at enhancing user experience, market positioning, and digital visibility. For the company's brand, the team developed a premium marketing strategy centred on digital engagement, influencer partnerships, and B2B expansion. Strategic approaches included LinkedIn campaigns, airline sales, and collaborations with vegan restaurants. Contributions focused on identifying key hospitality partners and enhancing the brand's visibility in niche markets. In a separate campaign promoting Harkány as a year-round tourist destination, the team applied AI-driven insights and culturally inclusive messaging to target foreign audiences. The result was a comprehensive digital strategy featuring personalised content, social media planning, and influencer engagement. AI tools were used to analyse traveller behaviour, optimise platform selection, and increase campaign effectiveness.

Team ID **15380296**

Challenge: Airbridge Go To Market

Summary of Challenge: The company needs to better explain how their smart delivery centres help different businesses; their main challenge is showing customers and partners why their tech-powered delivery system is better than traditional methods

Short description of results: The project resulted in an innovative, user-focused solution that improves accessibility and efficiency through AI-powered logistics optimisation, strategic market positioning, and sustainability-driven storytelling. The team collaborated effectively, integrating unique skill sets to enhance the company's smart delivery systems. By addressing inefficiencies in last-mile delivery with predictive analytics and automation, the project delivered a scalable strategy that improves operational performance, strengthens brand visibility, and reduces environmental impact. Contributions included leading the design phase, coordinating development efforts, and applying AI tools to optimise logistics in sectors such as healthcare and retail, enabling smarter, data-driven decision-making.

Team ID **15520304**

Challenge: Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

Summary of Challenge: develop innovative strategies that combine photography, graphic design, video production, and content creation to craft cohesive marketing campaigns for natural skincare and luxury spa

Short description of results: The team successfully implemented a functional chatbot using Tidio to improve customer interaction on the company's website. They enhanced brand visibility through educational, science-based SEO blog posts focused on skincare and wellness, tailored to audience interests and concerns. Their work also included developing a content strategy with a newsletter series plan, defining tone, messaging, and structure. A potential customer persona was created to guide communication efforts. In addition, the team conducted marketing research, compiled a list of promotional contacts, and improved the visual identity across digital channels. These combined efforts strengthened the company's online presence, customer engagement, and product communication.

Team ID **15590292**

Challenge: Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

Summary of Challenge: extend the open season of a restaurant beyond summer; develop a marketing campaign focused on foreign tourists; highlight cultural, historical, and natural attractions

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive marketing campaign titled "Tastes of Tradition, Served Fresh" to promote the company to both Hungarian locals and international tourists. Aimed at expanding visibility beyond the summer season, the campaign integrated trend research, customer personas, competitive analysis, and sustainability-driven messaging. Key strategies included digital-first outreach, personalised storytelling, influencer partnerships, and culturally inclusive content. Contributions were grounded in diverse areas of expertise: from crafting strategic communication and designing scalable digital tools, to aligning content with tourism trends and customer engagement needs. Digital engagement was enhanced through the use of data analytics, automation tools, and tailored social media materials. The result was a seasonal, experience-rich campaign concept designed to resonate with broad audiences and position the restaurant for long-term growth.

Team ID **15590347**

Challenge: Constructing a Creative Marketing Campaign to Attract Macedonian Generation Z Investors in Financial Services

Summary of Challenge: analyse students' and young adults' investment preferences; adapt existing products (at more applicable fees and other product flexibilities) and design an investment solution within company's regulatory restrictions

Short description of results: The team developed a creative, research-driven marketing campaign to engage Generation Z in North Macedonia with investing and financial literacy. Centred around a six-month Instagram strategy, the campaign used storytelling, digital tools, and interactive, visually engaging content to simplify financial concepts and promote smart money habits. The initiative was designed to be accessible, empowering, and aligned with Gen Z's values and media behaviours. As part of the broader "c-wallet" initiative, an independent educational social media platform set to merge with the main brand in the future, the team produced over 150 creative elements, including post formats, storylines, and engagement-focused content. Their work laid the foundation for a relatable, inclusive, and purpose-driven digital presence aimed at boosting financial confidence among young audiences.

Team ID **15620304**

Challenge: Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

Summary of Challenge: develop innovative strategies that combine photography, graphic design, video production, and content creation to craft cohesive marketing campaigns for natural skincare and luxury spa

Short description of results: The team developed a complete marketing strategy for a natural skincare and spa brand, aiming to strengthen its identity and boost its online presence. The project included competitor analysis, target audience research, and content development, featuring original designs, social media captions, and informative articles. Drawing on medical knowledge and content creation experience, the team produced educational blog posts and conducted expert interviews to build audience trust and product credibility. The resulting campaign highlights the brand's values and supports its growth through creative, targeted communication.

Team ID **15630292**

Challenge: Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

Summary of Challenge: extend the open season of a restaurant beyond summer; develop a marketing campaign focused on foreign tourists; highlight cultural, historical, and natural attractions

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive digital marketing strategy for a restaurant, aimed at attracting international and younger tourists while extending the restaurant's seasonal appeal. The strategy included a digital-first approach with tailored promotional campaigns, influencer partnerships, and seasonal content ideas. It also proposed sustainable menu innovations and staff training tools to enhance service quality and eco-conscious branding. Key deliverables included a campaign roadmap, strategic presentation materials, social media content, and a visually designed menu. Through audience analysis, brand refinement, and content planning, the project positioned the restaurant as an authentic and sustainable culinary destination in rural Hungary.

Team ID **15760354**

Challenge: Developing & Testing a Low-Cost Sustainable Insulation or Monitoring Solution for Temperature-Sensitive Logistics

Summary of Challenge: develop and validate a lightweight, biodegradable, and scalable packaging solution for cold chain logistics. focus on either: (A) developing a biodegradable insulation material to replace polystyrene in cold storage, or (B) embedding a simple, low-cost freshness or temperature indicator (e.g., colour-changing ink, basic sensor integration)

Short description of results: The study demonstrated the feasibility of developing a cost-effective, IoT-enabled temperature monitoring system for cold chain logistics within a virtual environment using the Wokwi simulator. The system, built around an ESP32 microcontroller and a DS18B20 temperature sensor, successfully measured temperatures and triggered real-time alarms when thresholds were exceeded. The team was responsible for designing the circuit, programming sensor integration and alert notifications, and performing virtual simulations to validate core functionalities. This virtual prototype offers a solid, low-cost foundation for future upgrades, including wireless data transfer and edge AI integration. The results highlight its potential to enhance reliability, operational efficiency, and environmental sustainability in cold chain systems.

Team ID **15790103**

Challenge: Innovative Custom-Made Hardwood Floors

Summary of Challenge: marketing approach for the launch of custom-made floors

Short description of results: The company is redefining ethical luxury in hardwood flooring by integrating blockchain-verified sustainability through the “Eco Passport,” AI/AR-driven personalisation, and federated AI for privacy-safe B2B targeting. The solution addresses greenwashing with transparent material tracing, offers real-time 3D product customisation, and identifies high-value clients, such as green hotels and modular builders, via predictive analytics. The project also introduced community engagement through the “Design for Earth” initiative, which gamifies product co-creation and allocates 5% of profits to reforestation efforts. The team’s contributions included trend analysis, strategic campaign design, and market analysis, shaping a forward-thinking approach to sustainable innovation and client engagement.

Team ID **15800179**

Challenge: Young People Live Sustainably

Summary of Challenge: develop a two-way communication campaign on living sustainably with a low-income targeting children and young people

Short description of results: The project focused on promoting sustainability among youth through a collaborative and educational campaign. The team developed a concept for a sustainability storytelling initiative, connecting young people, particularly from low-income backgrounds, through shared experiences and environmental values. This cross-border campaign aimed to build bonds between youth in Utrecht and a partner country by encouraging the exchange of personal sustainability stories. Key deliverables included a detailed communication and marketing proposal, a trend analysis of youth engagement in sustainability, a SWOT analysis of partner organisations, and the creation of marketing personas across three youth age groups. The team also compiled a contact database to support future outreach. Contributions ranged from brainstorming campaign ideas aligned with organisational goals, supporting team members throughout the process, and preparing research insights to guide campaign design and execution.

Team ID **15810346**

Challenge: Cellulose Reinvented

Summary of Challenge: developing the original activated carbon production methods

Short description of results: The team developed an innovative approach by using fly ash, a widely available industrial by-product, as the alkaline activating agent. This unconventional solution effectively enabled the chemical activation of cellulose and the development of nanoporosity in the resulting material. Activated carbon was successfully synthesised from secondary raw materials, including cellulose yarn and fly ash from a thermal power plant, transforming waste into a high-value product. The material demonstrated a specific surface area of approximately 500 m²/g. Surface chemistry analysis confirmed the presence of carboxyl, epoxy, and hydroxyl functional groups, indicating successful activation and broad potential for cross-industry applications. The project embraced circular economy principles by valorising waste and maximising resource efficiency. While the toxicity of the final product still requires verification, this issue could likely be resolved through appropriate selective precipitation methods.

Team ID **15830205**

Challenge: Marketing Campaign of the Future

Summary of Challenge: personalised marketing campaigns engaging diverse consumer segments and ensuring data privacy and security (manufacturer of luxury handmade bags, knitwear, and accessories)

Short description of results: The team developed a 5-week marketing campaign aimed at increasing the company's online sales and brand visibility. Centered on storytelling, sustainability, and community engagement, the campaign includes a strategic content plan and recommended tools tailored to support the company's transition to direct-to-consumer sales. The final campaign is implementation-ready and aligned with the brand's values and growth objectives.

Team ID **15850205**

Challenge: Marketing Campaign of the Future

Summary of Challenge: personalised marketing campaigns engaging diverse consumer segments and ensuring data privacy and security (manufacturer of luxury handmade bags, knitwear, and accessories)

Short description of results: The team developed a comprehensive marketing campaign for a Greek brand specialising in handmade bags and accessories. The strategy focused on

influencer collaboration, aiming to expand brand awareness and increase customer acquisition, particularly in the USA. Two core ideas were proposed: a commission-based model where influencers earn only upon generating sales, and a co-creation model involving the design of exclusive, limited-edition bags in partnership with selected influencers. As part of the campaign, the team conducted market research, created marketing personas, and performed a trend analysis to support data-driven decision-making. Regular consultations were held with the company's founder to refine the brand's marketing structure and suggest practical, real-life strategies to enhance visibility and sales. The outcome was a clear, creative, and actionable plan aligned with the company's identity and growth goals.

Team ID **16120190**

Challenge: Innovative Financial Health Reporting for Companies

Summary of Challenge: create a platform that generates a yearly and monthly financial health report for businesses

Short description of results: The team successfully completed the development and redesign of a web application for financial analysis, building on the work of a previous group for a Slovenian company. They reviewed and improved the existing codebase, implemented new features, and updated the visual design to enhance usability. Each member contributed through programming, feature development, and strategic input. One of the team's main strengths was conceptual development, with key contributions to user experience, content creation, and design improvements. The result is a fully functional, user-friendly application with upgraded features and a refreshed digital interface.

Team ID **16170292**

Challenge: Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

Summary of Challenge: extend the open season of a restaurant beyond summer; develop a marketing campaign focused on foreign tourists; highlight cultural, historical, and natural attractions

Short description of results: The project delivered a comprehensive digital marketing strategy for a restaurant, aimed at attracting international visitors and extending the restaurant's appeal beyond the summer season. The strategy included a multilingual website, AR-enhanced menus, interactive guest experiences, and tailored social media campaigns. Key elements also involved influencer partnerships and wellness-focused activities designed to boost off-season bookings and appeal to younger, experience-seeking travellers. The team conducted in-depth market research, analysed tourist segments, and explored Baranya's natural, cultural, and historical assets to align the campaign with local

tourism objectives. Strategic goals included a 25% increase in off-season bookings, 75% growth in website traffic, and 1,500+ new international visitors annually. Contributions spanned campaign co-development, bilingual branding, storytelling, and experience design, all supporting a modern, culturally rooted brand identity.

Team ID **16190161**

Challenge: Market analysis and trendspotting of automotive lighting products with focus on end customer

Summary of Challenge: get to know users and their expectations in automotive lighting; report how different groups perceive their needs and how to support those needs with light; compare different markets

Short description of results: The project team investigated end-user perceptions of automotive lighting through a cross-country survey and in-depth market analysis. Insights gathered were used to develop ten innovative lighting solutions aligned with emerging trends such as personalisation, sustainability, and vehicle-to-environment communication. These solutions were organised into six categories reflecting key user needs and future mobility scenarios. The team conducted data analysis, classified user insights, and translated findings into actionable innovation concepts. Contributions included market and customer experience analysis, user segmentation, development of visual materials and roadmaps, and preparation of the final strategic report. The project also fostered collaboration between students and companies in assessing market opportunities.

Team ID **16190173**

Challenge: Green Efficiency: Designing the Future Marketing Campaign for Connect IQ

Summary of Challenge: develop an innovative marketing campaign, focusing on promoting products for monitoring machine performance and energy consumption in industry

Short description of results: The international team developed a comprehensive strategic marketing campaign for Connect IQ, a smart monitoring solution tailored for small and medium-sized manufacturers. The campaign focused on increasing visibility and adoption across Europe by addressing key industry trends such as energy efficiency, sustainability, and regulatory compliance. The team conducted market research, trend analysis, and customer segmentation to guide the campaign's direction. Messaging was shaped around real industrial challenges, including rising energy costs and evolving EU regulations, and aligned with sustainability goals. Contributions included defining buyer personas, structuring cost-effective communication strategies, and creating targeted content to

engage manufacturers. The project successfully combined analytical and creative approaches to support smarter, more sustainable industrial practices.

Team ID **16190261**

Challenge: Marketing campaign for metal-forming defects sensors

Summary of Challenge: a marketing campaign dedicated to products used in the metal processing industry, namely plastic metalworking

Short description of results: The team delivered a trend-driven marketing strategy to promote IIoT solutions in the metal processing industry, with a focus on the automotive and household appliance sectors. The project involved market segmentation, trend and policy research, and the development of visual tools such as trend radar charts and impact-timing matrices. Strategic recommendations were tailored to align technological trends with campaign objectives. Contributions included audience segmentation, data visualisation, and value-driven messaging. The final outcome offers the company a well-structured, data-informed foundation for launching targeted marketing initiatives across key European markets.

III. STATISTICS ON CO-CREATION TEAMS

In the INDUSAC project, 318 individuals in 164 teams of students and researchers participated in co-creation projects. Since an individual may have participated in up to three co-creation teams, statistics are given on representation rather than the absolute number of students / researchers.

Number of team members per team (in line with the INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers, each team could include 3-6 members)

- 111 teams with three members (67,7 %)
- 27 teams with four members (16,5 %)
- 16 teams with five members (9,7 %)
- 10 teams with six members (6,1 %)

Number of teams in which students / researchers (318 in total) participated (in line with the INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers, each individual could participate in up to three teams):

- 140 in one team (44,0 %)
- 93 in two teams (29,3 %)
- 85 in three teams (26,7 %)

Number of researchers per team (in line with the INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers, each team had to include at least one student)

- o 138 teams included no researchers
- o 10 teams included 1 researcher
- o 12 teams included 2 researchers
- o 1 team included 3 researchers
- o 2 teams included 4 researchers
- o 1 team included 5 researchers

Gender distribution among participants in the co-creation projects:

- o 284 female (48.9 %)
- o 269 male (46.3 %)
- o 28 would rather not say (4.8 %)

Country of residency of participants of the co-creation teams:

Figure 1: Team members per country of residence. Widening countries are shown in green, other countries are shown in blue. Numbers were pooled from participants regardless of the number of teams they participated in (i.e., individuals may be counted more than once).

Distribution of participants by country of residency (581 in total, including students and researchers):

- 71 from EU Member states (12,2 %)
- 357 from EU widening countries (61,5 %)
- 153 from EU associated countries (26,3 %)

Country of university of participants of the co-creation teams (students only):

Figure 2: Student team members per country of university. Widening countries are shown in green, other countries are shown in blue. Numbers were pooled from participants regardless of the number of teams they participated in (i.e., individuals may be counted more than once).

Distribution of countries by country of university (530 in total, including students only):

- 60 from EU Member states (11,3 %)
- 367 from EU widening countries (69,3 %)
- 103 from EU associated countries (19,4 %)

Area of study (as provided in the registration form for the INDUSAC platform):

Table 1: Distribution of fields of study among student team members. Data (by %) for students registered on the INDUSAC platform, and for students participating in co-creation projects, is shown.

	Distribution of fields of study among INDUSAC students (in %)	
Field of Study	Students registered on the INDUSAC platform	Students participating in co-creation projects
Chemistry	11	14
Economic Sciences	23	23
Environment And Geoscience	6	8
Information Science And Engineering	31	30
Life Sciences	10	6
Mathematics	1.8	1.8
Social Sciences And Humanities	16	18
Physics	0.2	0.2

Figure 3: Number of student team members participating in the co-creation projects by fields of study.

Distribution of Challenges that were solved, by PCA type:

Figure 4: Representation of PCA types in the INDUSAC co-creation projects. PCA 1 - Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow, PCA 2 - Finding white spots in the product portfolio, PCA 3 - Marketing campaign of the future, PCA 4 - Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis, PCA 5 - Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona), PCA 6 - Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios), PCA 7 - Business plan - reduce your risk and optimise your planning, PCA 8 - Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain, and PCA 9 - Business model: Adding a service to my product - Building a PSS (product service system).

IV. FINAL REMARKS AND CONCLUSIONS

The INDUSAC project resulted in more than 160 successful collaborations between companies and teams of students and researchers. 318 individuals in 164 teams had the opportunity to experience working in an industry environment and build international networks. Gender balance was achieved as distribution across teams was 48.9 % female, 46.3 % male, and 4.8 % would-rather-not-say. Focus of the project was on EU widening countries, which had above 60-% overall representation by country of residency and by country of students' university, achieving the project goals in that respect as well. Challenges being solved were of entrepreneurial as well as technical nature, spanning all nine PCA types, most (around 46 %) being in the field of marketing campaign (PCA type 3 – Marketing campaign of the future), and around 18 % were focused on product development (PCA type 8 - Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain). This trend is consistent with the business landscape of participating companies, the majority of which were SMEs. SMEs often operate with limited internal capacity for research, development, and marketing innovation. They are typically more agile and growth-oriented but face resource constraints in strategic areas such as digital marketing, customer engagement, and product development. For these companies, co-creation offers a cost-effective and dynamic way to access fresh perspectives, creative ideas, and cutting-edge knowledge from academia. As such, challenges related to marketing and product innovation - areas with high impact and low capital investment requirements - were especially attractive to SMEs seeking quick wins or new directions. The popularity of PCA Type 3 also reflects broader trends in the digital economy, where effective communication strategies, social media engagement, and brand differentiation are essential for competitiveness. Meanwhile, PCA Type 8's focus on solving customer pain points aligns with a growing emphasis on user-centred design and lean innovation methods in product development, which are increasingly being adopted by SMEs to stay relevant and responsive to market needs. In conclusion, the INDUSAC project not only achieved its core objectives in terms of participation, diversity, and regional inclusion, but also demonstrated the viability of co-creation as a practical tool for innovation. The active involvement of SMEs and the distribution of challenge types underscore the relevance and adaptability of the co-creation model across different sectors and business functions. In many cases, the outcomes generated by the co-creation teams provided companies with valuable insights, prototypes, and research directions. At the same time, students and researchers gained practical experience and developed transferable skills, enhancing their career prospects. Looking ahead, the INDUSAC approach holds great potential for replication and scaling beyond the pilot phase. The platform and the processes established can serve as a blueprint for future initiatives seeking to bridge the gap between academic knowledge and industrial innovation.

V. LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Team members per country of residence.....	88
Figure 2: Student team members per country of university.)	89
Figure 3: Number of student team members participating in the co-creation projects by fields of study.....	91
Figure 4: Representation of PCA types in the INDUSAC co-creation projects.....	92

VI. LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Distribution of fields of study among student team members.....	90
--	----

